

An interpretative explanation of the wording of the arrest warrants for High State Public Elected Official of the Russian Federation (Part I)

By Bojidarka Ivanova[#]

[#]ORCID [<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5788-4404>]

Abstract

The study is intended to provide an interpretative explanatory view of the logic of *doing Justice* by the *Rome Statute*^[1] within the concept of category “*War crimes*” looking at Ukraine-Russia bilateral relations over recent few decades, however, tackling a case of arrest warrant texts (AWTs) for a High State Public Elected Official, *i.e.*, the President of the Russian Federation (hereafter **Subject 1**)^[2]. It aims at explaining and seeking meaning and understanding of evidences, facts, and arguments connected with developed and applied methods, concepts, theories, and laws used to *do Justice*; furthermore, used to International Criminal Tribunals (ICTs) over the recent 80 years. There is assumed a lack of prior knowledge of potential readers, and thus, I have not relied upon his, respectively, her in-depth knowledge of the matter. There is selected bibliography of only expert opinions. I think, that we can learn something from how in this case is tackled the issue of the shown category crimes within the *Rome Statute* without rejecting Norms. The focus is on how they are doubtfully and elusively used to interpret and apply legal terms developed for describing unlawful approaches to executive power authorities or “*a state or policy*” or both of these of compelling civil population; furthermore, *children*. In this case there is a lack of seeking beliefs as holding-true statements regarding qualification *accused*. The use of provision of justice frequently is associated with involvement of politics. It is called *Transitional Justice* and is as continuum between *purely political* and *purely legal* applications to *do Justice*. However, in **Subject 1-case**, the interpretation and application of the *Rome Statute* contradict the Human Right Law (HRL) applied to both victim groups and the hypothetical accused (**Subject 1**). In 2015, the European Union have adopted a supportive Policy regarding the *Transitional Justice* as part of implementation of an Action Plan on Human Rights and Democracy. However, a belief as holding-view cannot be used instead of seeking-true and holding-true statements. I have offered an analysis of real cases from ICTs-practice, so far, already interpreting and applying definitions of same crimes within the *international armed conflicts*. I have tried, I hope successfully to keep the content clear and accessible throughout, due to my major aim, *i.e.*, to make the reader aware of issue for which, perhaps, he, respectively, she never has thought. It is how an innocent individual (**Subject 1**) can be implicated in real criminal acts as a perpetrator when the interpretation and application of definitions of crimes is within the *Transitional Justice*. I should note that the Criminal Law is all domestic Systems with a penalty phase and there is the most corroborated theory based on evidences, facts, and arguments. In keeping the traditions of the Continental Systems most of evidences must be available prior any Trial. Thus, I hope that my potential readers shall grasp successfully a line of arguments which is not seen immediately, since the issue discussed is complex. However, it is of fundamental importance. The ‘War crimes’ are conduct type crimes; thus, examining primary *actus reus* of **Subject 1** as potential perpetrator or hypothetically accrued of committed crime individually (alone) in the crime scene. The essential understanding of the issue is that there is ‘act’ when committed as part of a widespread or systematic attack directed against any civilian population [children, herein]. Therefore, the perpetrator committed crime or it is individual committing or participating in the crime scene as co-perpetrator. Particularly, as great controversy has been regarded application of *mens rea* standard to this category crimes looking at ICTs-practice, so far. Among most debatable case is [IT-94-1-AR72] one. This study detail on cases of the ICTs-practice, showing that individuals, who have committed war crimes bear serious individual criminal responsibility, including imprisonment. The public’s perception of ICTs as doing Justice should be seriously undermined if there is wrong-punishment. The effort on best accomplishing aims of international justice at seeking-truth is directly related with reliability of evidences, which in **Subject 1-case** are not publicly available; thus, confusing a case involving High State Public Elected Official into case of war crimes, which, in fact, deals with crimes committed by small group (mostly a troop) mid-low level military individuals, who are directly subordinative and mutually connected mostly within the Executive Power Authorities

as well as reaching a '*relative autonomy*' during international military conflict, rather, assumes presence of false documents and testimony. The phenomenon is often found in war crime ICTs and is called '*evidence problem*'. Many examples of false testimony could be provided. For instance, these are [ICTR-96-4-IT], [ICTR-96-3-T], or [ICTR-95-1A-T], among others. Due to superimpose of the *actus reus* standard of war crimes, in case [ICTR-96-4-IT/09.03.1998] the Decision states: "...that only false testimony going to a material matter [actus reus] within the case is criminal"...The current text is agreed with, and does not contradict the Article 70 of the Rome Statute^[1].

Keywords: Rome Statute; interpretative-explanation; War-Crimes; Deportation; Forcible transfer of population; Law, Politics and International Relations, Russia.

Introduction

The major idea that the science as a crucial cornerstone, among others may have emerged of the human societies worldwide; thus, providing solution to specific problems, respectively, explaining and predicting various kinds of phenomena, including the social ones as attempt to enhance the living conditions of human life or the so-called human well-being and the technological progress of the society. Depending on object there are three major branches of the modern science, *i.e.*, *natural*, *social*, and *human* one. In a democratic society, it is particularly important that the citizens should be informed not only about what are these scientific branches; how are they distinguished; and, in parallel interact mutually, but also how the scientific knowledge is applied to the practice or to the society.

Therefore, researchers and interpreters of scientific knowledge should be able to enter into critical dialogue with the audience regarding definitions of scientific objects, respectively, subjects and how they are applied to the society.

The latter issue is of particular importance, owing to the fact that the modern societies are confronted daily *via media* with news regarding military conflicts, mass atrocities, (civil) war, and various crimes committed during these armed conflicts. Frequently, there is offered to the audience only fragments of the realities of these conflicts, which, presumably, should be tackled as 'facts', 'arguments', or, even as evidences. Often, there is impeded real understanding and comprehension of events, moreover there are a diverse of courses, causes, and consequences of events and processes.

Furthermore, any case is different from any other one in addition to the fact that it requires specific knowledge in order one to be able to tackle the issue adequately.

Therefore, we need a general account of adequacy in tackling these events, because of, within the framework of the so-called concept of '*Protection of nationals*' there is conducting of a military operation in territory of a state, however, aiming at protecting or rescuing or both of these of the treated nations of the so-called *intervening country*^[3]. The latter operations, however, are called '*humanitarian intervention*' or *humanitarian military operation*' involving use of force. They are induced as an attempt to prevent (additional) harm to domestic individuals or group citizens in a territory of another state^[3]. It is agreed, that from a legal perspective the various type of military operations, including the '*humanitarian intervention*' should be kept separate^[3].

However, various legal concepts dealing with the notion *military operation* are objects of on-going debates, including the '*Protection of nationals*' one^[3,4]; thus, continuously providing pro- and con-arguments among a variety of legal basis in supporting or rejecting views.

Looking at Ukraine-Russia bilateral relations over the recent few decades, it should be said that the readers should confine themselves to accept them as '*conflicts*' according to the cited references, above. This study lacks of reviewing of the large body of the literature devoted to the latter issue.

However, there should be shed more light on the main two views tackling the nature of the international armed conflicts:

(i) There is "*humanitarian military operation*" which does not infringe prohibition on utilizing force according to Article 2(4) of the UN Charter^[5]. It does not impair the '*territorial integrity or political*

independence' of a state. It rescues domestic nationals from a danger which the territorial state cannot or will not prevent^[6].

The second view, which is more widespread supported holds that:

(ii) The national groups of a territory exercise of right of self-defence and self-determination^[7]. The rights for self-determination are defined within the framework of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) which is in force of 23.03.1976. It is in accordance with Article 49 (consider [<https://www.ohchr.org/en/instruments-mechanisms/instruments/international-covenant-civil-and-political-rights>]).

Article 1 (ICCPR)

1. All peoples have the right of self-determination. By virtue of that right they freely determine their political status and freely pursue their economic, social and cultural development.
2. All peoples may, for their own ends, freely dispose of their natural wealth and resources without prejudice to any obligations arising out of international economic co-operation, based upon the principle of mutual benefit, and international law. In no case may a people be deprived of its own means of subsistence.
3. The States Parties to the present Covenant, including those having responsibility for the administration of Non-Self-Governing and Trust Territories, shall promote the realization of the right of self-determination, and shall respect that right, in conformity with the provisions of the Charter of the United Nations (UN).

A pro-argument for view (ii) is that the inclusion in UN Charter of *inherent* right of self-defence has left unabridged the broader pre-existing customary right of self-defence. *Inter alia* the issue extended to the protection of nationals.

A view (iii) has argued for nationals abroad form part of a state's population. An essential attribute, which is implied, among others is that an attack against nationals abroad can be equated to an attack against the state itself, thus triggering Article 51 of the UN Charter^[8].

It should be added that under '*attacks against the civilian population*' there is understood acts intending to spread terror, as well. If we do take talk of views (I)–(iii) seriously, then we must at this point stress that major area connected with Ukraine-Russia conflict could be relatively easy assigned to Donbass (a large of Eastern Ukraine.) The history of Ukraine can be sent back in 1915, when the Ukraine's Claim to Freedom *via* pamphlet published by New Jersey's Ukrainian National Association and Pennsylvania's Ruthenian National Union, demanding autonomy for Russian Ukraine and "a self-governed province" not dominated by the Poles or their aristocracy. According to *Europäisches Russland; Stielers Schul-Atlas* (Justus Perthes 1829), Suppl. III (p.90 [<https://archive.org/details/adstielersschula00stie/page/n89/mode/2up>]), it consists of four areas called Gubernii, *i.e.*, Kiev, Chernigov, Poltava, and Kharkov (consider **supporting information file 1**). Since 30.12.1922 Ukraine belongs to Russian Soviet Federative Socialist Republic (RSFSR) as Ukraine SSR until 1991 [Verkhovna Rada of the Soviet Socialist Republic of Ukraine, "Declaration on state sovereignty of Ukraine," Pub. L. No. 55-XII (1990), <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/go/55-12>].

Due to these historical reasons, the Donbass together with a large area until Dnepr in the Eastern part of Ukraine is mainly populated by Russian ethnics and Russian speaking citizens; furthermore, within 74–98 %^[9]. There are 24.4 % ethnic Russian minority in Ukraine since 08.12.1991^[10] (the all-Ukrainian referendum dates 01.12.1991) and at about 51.1 % of ethnic Russian minority populated chiefly Donbass.

The latter data quickly turn into conceptual views (I)–(iii) detailing on various international military operations; thus, allowing us to conclude that particularly the events in Ukrainian territory within the 01.09.2014–24.02.2022 are directly connected mostly with the Russian ethnic Minority and those Russian speaking Ukrainians self-determining themselves as Russians.

The sharp spatial polarity of the Ukrainian Society between the Eastern and Western territory justifies the involvement into debates the concept of protection of nationals or concept of protection of the Russian minority group in Ukraine. Moreover, it is claimed that it [the concept] is difficult to fit off predetermining legal categories. Rather, it constitutes autonomously under Article 2(4)^[11].

The attentive reader might have already noticed striking difference among views that can be proposed as military operation types allowing us to understand events, therein particularly over span of time 01.09.2014–24.02.2022, and those ones observed since 24.02.2022. I do not discuss the adequacy of available concepts of various military operations. I only sketch them.

The previous paragraphs, however, aims at accounting for the first problem with the AWTs-wording of **Subject 1-case**^[2]. Both the texts [2(a)] and [2(b)] have stated:“.... *at least from 24 February 2022...*”.

The date corresponds to begin with military operation by the Army of the Russian Federation in a territory called Donetsk People’s Republic (DNR) (**Figures 1 and 2**), not Ukraine. The DNR together with Luhansk People’s Republic (LNR) represent a part of Donbass. The DNR and LNR are determined as Oblasti with domestic self-governing authority within the Law of Special Statute according to multilateral Agreement Minsk II (Protocol/01.09.2014; Article 9, signed by the Second President of Ukraine, among others [<https://www.osce.org/files/f/documents/a/a/123258.pdf>]).

Figure 1. Some Codes and legal applications of War crimes and definitions of deportation and forcible transfer of population under Article 8 (2); some Federal Laws (FL) and Presidential Decrees.

[1] H. von Hebel, D. Robinson, 'Crimes Within the Jurisdiction...', chapter 2, Brill, 1999, ISBN: 9789040315157 [https://doi.org/10.1163/9789040315157_009]. [2] Report of the Independent International Commission of Inquiry on the Syrian Arab Republic, A/HRC/43/57, para. 80 [<https://docs.un.org/en/A/HRC/43/57>]. [3] (a) [<https://www.unhcr.org/refugees/1949/article-49>]. (b) [<https://www.unhcr.org/refugees/1949/article-50>]. [4] Prosecutor v. Radislav Krstić, judgement, Case No. IT-98-22, 2 August 2001, para. 521 [<https://www.cjic.org/cases/krstic/judgments/010802a.pdf>]. [5] T. Remington, Patronage and Power: Russia's Dominant Party Regime, PVS, 45, 213-226 (2009) [<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11615-009-0097-y>]. [6] T. Remington, Patronage and the Party of Power: President's Parliament Relations under Vladimir Putin, Europe-Asia Studies, Aug. 2008, Vol. 60, No. 6, Power and Policy in Putin's Russia (Aug., 2008), pp. 959-987 [<https://doi.org/10.1080/09688130802161215>].

Figure 2. Some Administrative Units of the Russia Federation; and hypothetical groups of children-victims 1A, 1B, and 2C who could belong to deported groups depending on 'peace' or 'wartime' of committed crimes; if any, as well as special statute of territories according to Minsk II Agreement, while groups children 1C and 2C could belong to transferred children, depending on statute of the territory.

Minsk II Agreement states [<https://www.osce.org/files/f/documents/a/a/123258.pdf>]:

Article 3

...*"on local self-government in the separated areas of Donetsk and Luhansk regions..."* (Law on Special Status (of these regions).)
(Consider Article 6 and Article 9, as well.)

Explicitly, I stress on the fact that both the DNR and LNR since 01.09.2014 or 17.02.2015 (**Figure 3**) are *self-governing Oblasti*. The latter remark on is regarding the Article 1(3) of ICCPR, shown above, which treats *non-self-governing Oblasti*.

If we admit the Minsk II Agreement, then the military operation by RA in a territory having a *special statute* (DNR), and presumably lacks Ukrainian Armed Forces, therein, according to Article 10 of the same Protocol [<https://www.osce.org/files/f/documents/a/a/123258.pdf>]); and, does not belong [the discussed territory] to Ukraine, then the conflict cannot be regarded as Ukraine-Russia one. Therefore, the date 24.02.2022 cannot be assigned to a military operation by RA in the territory of Ukraine. If it is so, then there is, first, a lack of an act of crossing Ukraine-Russia State border. The events on 24.02.2022, therefore cannot be linked with Ukraine as the AWTs^[2] have informed us.

Of course, one would reject the Minsk II Agreement. Then, date 24.02.2022 is associated with the Ukraine-Russia conflict.

However, in this case, there is, a second. The date 24.02.2022 cannot be regarded as date of beginning of military conflict, despite the fact that it is the date when RA across the DNR-Russia border. In the context of the wording of the AWTs^[2] the date, perhaps, refers to RA's act in crossing the

Ukraine-Russia State border. However, let me hasten to add that if the date 24.02.2022 is accepted by AWTs^[2] as referring to the latter act, then this should mean that it does not accept the Minsk II Agreement, because of there is a lack of 'in Donetsk People's Republic (Oblast) (17.05.2015–30.09.2022)", as well. Because, both the Minsk I and Minsk II Agreements are endorsed by UN Security Council Resolution 2022 as **Figure 3** shows. The document can be found, herein [Resolutionen und Beschlüsse des Sicherheitsrats vom 1. August 2014 bis 31. Juli 2015; https://www.un.org/depts/german/sr/sr_14-15/sr2202.pdf]].

Figure 3. Spatial-temporal distribution of events in Ukraine during the recent decade.

Key problem (1): The wording of AWTs^[2] of **Subject 1-case** lacks of nature of events associated with Ukraine and dating on "...at least from 24.02.2022" in context of neither nature of military operation of the Army of the Russian Federation nor statute of Donetsk People's Republic (Oblast) (17.05.2015–30.09.2022).

A particular remark on the latter context is associated with the fact, that there is already statement: "continues to examine allegations that the Russian Federation has exercised overall control over armed groups in eastern Ukraine" regarding the Eastern Ukraine, involving Donbass (p. 95 https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/itemsDocuments/2017-PE-rep/2017-otp-rep-PE_ENG.pdf)).

Presumably, this indicates that the SOFA Agreement between Ukraine and Russia is accepted, as valid as it is actually in force of 07.12.1999 https://web.archive.org/web/20140321072522/http://www.mid.ru/bdomp/spd_md.nsf/0/BBC88CF0F9DF3F9F44257C9800383F4D].

One special consideration assumes that the preceding paragraphs provide correct interpretation of the wording of the AWTs^[2]; thus, stressing, however, on key problem (2).

Key problem (2): The AWTs^[2] lack of a complete list of bi- and multilateral Agreements involving the so-called Party State Ukraine and Russia together with third States; if any, which the AWTs' events encompass. There are a set of already signed Agreements over the latter three decades of the Ukraine-Russia (bi- and multilateral) relationships.

The key problem (2) is directly connected with the definition of crime 'Deportation' which legal application requests definition of the so-called *State Border*, however.

In other words, does the Border between Russia and DNR-Oblast during that time (24.02.2022) is regarded as State border Ukraine-Russia, or it is border between a territory with a special statute (DNR-Oblast) and Russia?

Perhaps, the reader will note that the focus of the introductory section, so far concentrates on term '*State Border*', thus, giving it genuinely significance. It is connected with legal definitions of '*deportation*' and forcible, in fact "transfer", as aforementioned. It is easy to see that further care is requested. Concepts providing an understanding of the issue from perspective of ICTs-practice shall be presented in the following sections. As the reader should be convinced, I strongly hope persuasively, we unable to verify the beliefs regarding committed crimes by **Subject 1**; his intension of committing crimes; and more, which shall be detailed further, without interpreting what the wording of the AWTs^[2] means, in fact.

The cycle of understanding of the AWTs^[2] wording includes adequate interpretation of what the texts themselves belief. Depending on descriptive and explanatory adequacy we shall be able to justifiably ascribe the reasoning to the AWTs.

Thus, we attempt, first, to resolve the debate about the nature of the Ukraine-Russia conflict which is directly connected with the AWTs-wording^[2], but without knowing the exact timed-framework of the hypothetical committed crimes. It is only written '*.... at least from 24 February 2022...*'. Looking at the dynamics of the sketched events of Ukraine-Russia relations (**Figure 1**), there could be sharply distinguished at least four periods (I–IV) dating since 1915. Some important data on the pre-history of the conflict associated with Donbass could be found^[9]. They tackle a period 01.09.2014–24.02.2022. Does it mean that the wording '*.... at least from 24 February 2022...*' should be understood as applicable to period 01.09.2014–24.02.2022?

Because of, we could also deduce that under the two words "*at least*" of the wording '*.... at least from 24 February 2022...*'^[2] there is understood the date on the first **Subject 1**'s Presidential mandate (7.05.2000). Why? He has occupied various High State Public Elected Positions over the recent two decades.

Looking at the AWTs^[2]-wording addressed to **Subject 1**, relevant beliefs of committed crimes addressed to him differ significantly from ours seems obvious requirements for such cases of concreteness and precise wording used to elaborate arguments. Instead of, there is further **Key Problem (3)** associated with a lack of occupied position of **Subject 1** encompassing the investigated crimes; if any *at the time of the alleged conduct*. It is only shown '*President of the Russian Federation*'^[2].

Conversely, if there is detailed on wording of the arrest warrants of **Subject 3** and **Subject 4** again involved into beliefs of committed crimes, then it becomes immediately apparent the fact that there is written: '*.... Minister of Defence of the Russian Federation at the time of the alleged conduct*' or '*Chief of the General Staff of the Armed Forces of the Russian Federation and First Deputy Minister of Defence of the Russian Federation at the time of the alleged conduct*'. Consider the wording of the texts of arrest warrants addressed to **Subject 3** and **Subject 4**: [<https://www.icc-cpi.int/defendant/shoigu>]; and [<https://www.icc-cpi.int/defendant/gerasimov>].

Key problem (3): Does the shown in the AWTs^[2] High State Position of Public Elected Official occupied currently by **Subject 1** corresponds to “*at the time of the alleged conduct*”?

Despite the fact that, herein, I should not detail on wording of arrest warrant texts against **Subject 3** and **Subject 4**, I shall only stress that looking at their formulation and comparing with AWTs^[2], a double standard of writing is obvious.

The problems of exact fixing both period(s) associated with beliefs of committed crimes addressed to **Subject 1** and his concrete administrative position ‘*at the time of the alleged conduct*’ should be tackled precisely, because of **Subject 1** has occupied not only non-subsequent mandates as President of the Russian Federation, but also various levels of other High State Administrative Positions of Public Elected Official. Owing to history of Ukraine-Russia conflict dating far back the 24.02.2022, ambiguity of AWTs-wording^[2] and a lack of concreteness of span of time associated with beliefs of committed crimes could assume more than one Presidential mandate or even other High State Administrative Position of Public Elected Official.

However, as **Figure 1** attempts to illustrate, the dynamics of legislature even looking a hypothetical span of time 01.09.2014–24.02.2022 is significant in the Russian Federation. Therefore, there is requested fixed timed-framework of hypothetically committed crimes, together with fixed exact High State Administrative Position of Public Elected Official within a strict spatial-temporal distribution of hypothetical crime cases; furthermore, case-by-case, due to reasons sketched, below.

Apart, from **key problem (3)**, let us further interpret “.... *at least from 24 February 2022...*”^[2] in context of period of intensifying the conflict narrative between Ukraine and Russia, *i.e.*, since 01.09.2014 (Minsk II Agreement); thus, focusing the reader attention on span of time 01.09.2014–24.02.2022. It is very far from lacking problems, however in attempting to associate it with Ukraine-Russia conflict.

As **Figure 3** shows on 30.04.2014, due to significant intensity of hostilities, there is classified events in Ukraine as belonging to “*parties to a non-international armed conflict*” (p. 22 [https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/itemsDocuments/2017-PE-rep/2017-otp-rep-PE_ENG.pdf][donbass]). There is explicitly stated that the conflict “*occurs between the government of a state and one or more internal opposition groups with intervention from other states.*” [https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/itemsDocuments/2017-PE-rep/2017-otp-rep-PE_ENG.pdf].

Looking at these statements obvious problems and further questions are raised and settled, regarding not only exact timed-framework of hypothetically committed crimes addressed to **Subject 1** as accused, but also to so-called ‘*State responsibility*’ and “*State party in the conflict*”, which shall be subsequently detailed on, as well.

At this point, I would like to consider the fact that, if there is already classified the conflict as ‘*non-international conflict*’ [https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/itemsDocuments/2017-PE-rep/2017-otp-rep-PE_ENG.pdf] in the territory of Ukraine, then on 01.09.2014 the Minsk II Agreement has established DNR and LNR as novel separated self-governed Oblasti, having special statutes, as aforementioned. As has been already explicitly highlighted, on 17.05.2015 UN Security Council (Resolution 2222) endorsed both the novel Oblasti; thus, providing novel legal statute of DNR and LNR.

Thus, a statement dating on 30.04.2014 and classifying the conflict [https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/itemsDocuments/2017-PE-rep/2017-otp-rep-PE_ENG.pdf] as “non-international” one becomes inapplicable to events hypothetically committed over span of time 17.05.2015–24.02.2022, due to difference in international statute of the two novel self-governed territorial units (DNR and LNR). The span of time 30.04.2014–17.05.2015, therefore, cannot be extended to date 30.04.2014. In other words, events committed within 30.04.2014–17.05.2015 cannot

be classified as non-international conflict only looking at statement [https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/itemsDocuments/2017-PE-rep/2017-otp-rep-PE_ENG.pdf].

Further: On 30.09.2022 the DNR becomes *via* referendum a part of the Russian Federation. Thus, within the 17.05.2015–30.09.2022 DNR is self-governed Oblast part of conflict; thus, making it ‘Oblast Party in the conflict’. The conflict, therefore, is Ukraine-DNR international one.

I would like to emphasise that this position that I would like to defend, herein, and I would defend it persuasively, is not a hypothetical one. Rather, it is of significant importance from the perspective of the major purpose of this contribution. The position, rather, needs to be stressed.

Looking at definitions of the crimes of *deportation* and (forcible) *transfer* of population [children in this case] together with numerous documents regarding hypothetical crimes as cited, herein, ones together with those presented in **Figure 3** within the 17.05.2015–30.09.2022 cannot be assigned to territory internal neither to Ukraine nor to Russia. Why?

Case [IT-97-24-T/31.07.2003], [[<https://www.refworld.org/jurisprudence/caselaw/icty/2003/en/40192>]; (§673, §679)] stated that Article 5(d) of the Statute of the International Criminal Tribunal for the Former Yugoslavia (ICTY) [https://www.icty.org/x/file/Legal%20Library/Statute/statute_sept09_en.pdf]; ‘*crimes against humanity*’ must be read to “encompass forced population displacements both across internationally recognised borders and *de facto* boundaries, such as constantly changing frontlines, which are not internationally recognised”.

Therefore, both the statute of DNR and LNR as well as the nature of Ukraine-Russia conflict are constantly misunderstood. They should be classified both the longer (temporal) and wider (spatial). In so doing, there can be sharply distinguished the following conflict scenes involving armed forces in Ukraine, starting; for instance, since 30.04.2014:

- (A) 30.04.2014–17.02.2015: Non international armed conflict in Ukraine, excluding Russia; and
- (B) 17.02.2015–30.09.2022: International armed conflict involving Ukraine as Party State and DNR as Party Oblast in the conflict, again excluding Russia as Party State in the conflict.

Because of, on 24.02.2022 the Russia is involved into international humanitarian intervention by invitation into DNR Oblast as a separated Party Oblast in the conflict Ukraine-DNR (Oblast) during that time, in fact.

The chronology of events, shows:

On 26.05.2014: There is escalation of armed scenes formally starts end of May in DNR^[9]. During that time, DNR still belong to Ukraine territory and, thus, the conflict is non-international one.

On 12.06.2014: 51th, 72th, 24th, and 28th mechanized brigades; also, 79th airmobile brigades of Ukrainian army start establishment of control of border (p. 129^[32].) using heavy weapons.

On 05.05.2014: Ukrainian armed forces re-established control over towns in Donetsk and Luhansk Republics (p. 129^[32].)

Circa 15.07.2014: 80th airmobile brigade, 24th brigade, battalion ‘Aidar’, 1st tank brigade of Ukrainian armed forces have started fighting on communication linking Luhansk with Russian border (p. 129^[32].) Heavy armed (Ukrainian) battalions and border guard units reinforced ca. 3000 fighters at about 150 km from Amvrosiivka and Izvaryne (p. 131^[32]) (Izvaryne is Donetsk checkpoint with Russia.)

On 12.08.2014: Same Ukrainian military forces captured Vuhlehirsk near Debaltseve; put pressure on Horlivka garrison, captured Khriashchuvate (ca. 30 km from Russia's border) and Novosvitlivka, respectively.

All sketched events above are assigned to non-international armed conflict in Ukraine, excluding Russia as Party State in it, but against the Russian ethnic Minority, therein. Within the 30.04.2014–24.02.2022 there is a lack of Russian Executive Authorities neither in territory of Ukraine, nor in the territory of DNR or LNR as State Army part in the conflict. Explicitly! Therefore, from the perspective of Ukraine-Russian conflict the latter period can be classified as “peace time-phase”.

A reasonable question would be why there is needed such classification of various phases of the Ukraine-Russia conflict? It is also connected with definitions of crimes under Article 8^[1] (below).

The interpretation of events and facts mentioned indicate that on 24.02.2022, RA perform *humanitarian intervention* in territory of self-governed Oblast DNR, and the application of the legal term *deportation* becomes inapplicable to transfer children across Ukraine-Russia State border, because of, first there is *humanitarian intervention* which do not impair 'territorial integrity or political independence' of a state. Second, there is crossed, in fact DNR-Oblast-Russia border.

Further: Despite the nature or a classification of armed conflicts there is in force of Article 50 of the Fourth Geneva Convention of 1949 and it updates; for instance, Rules in the Additional Protocol I (see Article 77). There is protection [of the children] against the effects of war [[<https://ihl-databases.icrc.org/en/ihl-treaties/gciv-1949/article-50?activeTab=>] by the Army of the Russian Federation or the Russian Border Control Authority or both of these. Even, if there is accepted as reality the data on presence of the Ukrainian armed forces on the Russian State border still on 05.05.2014, then a transfer of population [children]; if any, involves both the Ukrainian and Russian Executive Power Authorities, however.

The AWTs^[2]-wording lacks of seeking-responsibility from neither Ukraine nor individuals from the Ukrainian Executive Authorities.

If it is the armed scene on 24.02.2022, then there should be crucial objection of AWTs^[2]-wording toward the conflict-location. It should be in DNR-Oblast; and thus, claims by Ukraine as State Party against Russia are unjustifiable. Ukraine, in fact, can be regarded even as “Aggressor-Party-State” in the territory of DNR separated from Ukraine as Oblast with the UN Security Council (Resolution 2022) dating on 17.05.2015.

As the reader is already, perhaps convinced, there is difficult question highlighted as Key problem (1), *i.e.*, what there should be understood under ...”at least 24 February 2022” in the context of “in Ukraine”. It cannot be answered in a paragraph.

The distinction between *humanitarian intervention* by RA in the territory of DNR-Oblast dating since 24.02.2022 and Ukraine-Russia conflict becomes more debatable. Why? A timed-framework of the conflict can be classified as *ethnic cleaning* of Russian ethnics populating until 24.02.2022 in the Eastern territory of Ukraine, but within the 2015–2019^[9,12] or within the 30.04.2014–24.02.2022 according to the analysis, herein. The events within the fixed above timed-framework are different from the events during 2013-2014^[9]. They are associated with killing of people in the Ukrainian territory by Ukrainian Executive Authorities. It is performed, rather, due to difference in political views (pro-EU against pro-Russian Federation movements within the 2013–2014). The temporal-spatial interpretation of events and facts, herein rather assumes that, there is shifting in nature of committed crimes from *politicide* (central Ukraine 2013–2014) to *ethnic cleaning* against ethnic Russians in Eastern Ukraine, and mainly the self-governed Oblast DNR (30.04.2014–24.02.2022.)

In concluding this section what I have explored, so far, is that the AWTs^[2] do not tackle adequately many issues regarding neither the nature of events happened on date “*at least from 24 February 2022*”, nor various periods of Ukraine-Russia conflict, which are distinguished sharply not only even looking at them temporally or at their timed-framework; for instance, 01.09.2014–24.02.2022, but also spatially in classifying the committed crimes by Ukrainian Executive Authorities during that time against the ethnic Russian population within the Central and Eastern Ukraine and the separated Oblasti DNR and LNR.

The AWTs^[2] do not tackle adequately many issues connected with the rights of neither potential victims [children], nor the hypothetical accused **Subject 1**, as well. The straightforward interpretation and application of legal terms toward beliefs as holding-view toward hypothetically committed crimes appears embedded in the discussed AWTs^[2] in a far broader, doubtful, ambiguous and elusive context that the particular theories and concepts behind the terms inclining narrow application and grasping a particular meaning of crimes that they play in fact according to the already established ICTs-practice. Due to these reasons, the following section deals with briefly definitions term-by-term of the discussed crimes and their practical application to numerous cases, so far.

1. The wording of the arrest warrants – a legal meaning

To begin with, ideally, the *do Justice* concept want to provide a sound legal foundation for *doing Justice*; furthermore, internationally within the framework of the concept of *international crimes* (p. 21^[13]) *via* the *Rome Statute*^[1], the Rules of Procedure (Article 51) and the Elements of Crimes (ECs) (Article 9)^[13]. Their jurisdiction is over few categories of crimes^[13,14]. This contribution concentrates on a case categorized within the so-called *War Crimes* under Article 8 of the Rome Statute^[1].

Article 8 (War crimes)

Article 9 (Elements of Crimes)

1. *Elements of Crimes shall assist the Court in the interpretation and application of articles 6, 7 and 8.*

Article 51 (Rules of Procedure and Evidence)

(Comprehensive analysis of mechanisms of *do Justice via* the Rome Statute, the interested reader could find in works^[15–17], among others.)

The focus on mechanisms of *doing Justice via* interpreting and applying the Rome Statute is directly connected with legal definitions and their cognitive meaning within the framework of the various theories that are used to practice. In order to understand the logic of *doing justice* we should have a reliable interpretation of legal terms which should be able to yield understanding of the Rome Statute, itself and its logic of applying.

A reliable understanding is a process allowing us for a reasonable understanding of its interpreters, as well. The process of interpretation of the Rome Statute means in fact its explanation. Therefore, the current attempt in interpreting the Rome Statute is a kind of explanation of something that is previously not in-depth understood or not well defined.

At this point, perhaps, one would turn to my statement above that there is comprehensive reading allowing us to tackle the issue unambiguously looking for instance works^[15–17]. However, the analytical statements could express either tautologies or synonymities. Frequently, this causes for contradicting applications of already defined terms. In this particular **Subject 1-case** case of wording of AWTs^[2] the interested reader shall find a kind of interpretative explanation of the Rome Statute based on definitions used to classify crimes under Article 8^[1] already applied to numerous cases of ICTs, so far. Why there is used interpretative explanation of the text? Owing to the fact that the interpreted text represents something other than wording and subsequence of Laws of the Rome Statute, but anything

is causally connected with another things, the mutual connection among these things, therefore should be understood as that one thing might plausibly said represents the other(s) one(s).

Thus, a reliable understanding of the logic of *doing Justice* is directly connected with not only explanation, but also interpretation of the Rome Statute and some practices of application of the Criminal Codes by ICTs as still the section Abstract has remarked on.

Since, the interpretation of the Rome Statute is joined with description of its System of Laws and application of the logic of *doing Justice* practically, in what follows there is interpreted the text of available legal definitions of hypothetically committed crimes according to AWTs^[2]:

"Situation in Ukraine: [...] arrest warrants against **Subject 1** and **Subject 2** (Press Release: 17 March 2023)
Today, 17 March 2023, [...] issued warrants of arrest for two individuals in the context of the situation in Ukraine: Mr **Subject 1** and Ms **Subject 2**.
Mr **Subject 1**, born on XXX, President of the Russian Federation, is allegedly responsible for the war crime of unlawful deportation of population (**children**) and that of unlawful transfer of population (children) from occupied areas of Ukraine to the Russian Federation (under **articles 8(2)(a)(vii) and 8(2)(b)(viii) of the Rome Statute**). The crimes were allegedly committed **in Ukrainian occupied territory at least from 24 February 2022**. There are reasonable grounds to believe that Mr **Subject 1** bears individual criminal responsibility for the aforementioned crimes, (i) for having committed the acts directly, jointly with others and/or through others (**article 25(3)(a) of the Rome Statute**), and (ii) for his failure to exercise control properly over civilian and military subordinates who committed the acts, or allowed for their commission, and who were under his effective authority and control, pursuant to superior responsibility (**article 28(b) of the Rome Statute**).
Ms **Subject 2**, born on XXX, Commissioner for Children's Rights in the Office of the President of the Russian Federation, is allegedly responsible for the war crime of unlawful deportation of population (children) and that of unlawful transfer of population (children) from occupied areas of Ukraine to the Russian Federation (under **articles 8(2)(a)(vii) and 8(2)(b)(viii) of the Rome Statute**). The crimes were allegedly committed **in Ukrainian occupied territory at least from 24 February 2022**. There are reasonable grounds to believe that Ms **Subject 2** bears individual criminal responsibility for the aforementioned crimes, for having committed the acts directly, jointly with others and/or through others (**article 25(3)(a) of the Rome Statute**).
[...] based on the Prosecution's applications of 22 February 2023, that there are reasonable grounds to believe that each suspect bears responsibility for the war crime of unlawful deportation of population and that of unlawful transfer of population from occupied areas of Ukraine to the Russian Federation, in prejudice of Ukrainian children.
The [...] considered that the warrants are secret in order to protect victims and witnesses and also to safeguard the investigation. Nevertheless, mindful that the conduct addressed in the present situation is allegedly ongoing, and that the public awareness of the warrants may contribute to the prevention of the further commission of crimes, the [...] considered that it is in the interests of justice to authorise the Registry to publicly disclose the existence of the warrants, the name of the suspects, the crimes for which the warrants are issued, and the modes of liability as established by the Chamber.
The above-mentioned warrants of arrests were issued pursuant to the applications submitted by the Prosecution on 22 February 2023"^[2(a)]. There is also a text of arrest warrant addressing the same issue (please, consider^[2(b)])).

There are listed the following Articles of the Rome Statute^[1]: Article 8(2)(a)(vii), Article 8(2)(b)(viii), Article 25(3)(a), and Article 28(b) (**Subject 1**) as well as Article 8(2)(a)(vii), Article 8(2)(b)(viii), and Article 25(3)(a) (**Subject 2**). The same Articles addressed to **Subject 1** can be found in AWT^[2(b)].

There is assumed that the two AWTs [2(a)] and [2(b)] addressed to **Subject 1** are associated with the same hypothetical commitments of same crimes; if any, involving the name of **Subject 1**; and, **Subject 1** is the same individual, *i.e.*, the current President of the Russian Federation to date; for example, today 05.09.2025. Thus, what we would conclude looking at the wording of the AWTs^[2]?

1.1. *On the individuals whom should be understood as "children" potential victims of crimes of deportation and (forcible) transfer*

The AWTs^[2] show obvious deficiencies of exact number of “*population*” (children), victims of the discussed crimes; if any; their gender, ages, nationality, ethnicity, and status. The necessity of the latter data is due to the following reasons.

According to media and literature there is: “*In total, by spring 2023 almost 500 children had been killed and more than 500 injured. By July 2023, Ukraine estimated that nearly 20 000 Ukraine children had been abducted*^[18,19]”.

Let us assume that the latter number of hypothetical victims children links to the AWTs^[2]-wording.

Immediately, there is apparent ‘*Ukraine estimated*’...and “*Ukrainian children*”. However, does the word ‘*Ukrainian*’ used to the hypothetical victims, mean their nationality or it is their ethnicity? As aforementioned, there is significant heterogeneity of the spatial distribution of ethnic Russians and ethnic Ukrainians in the Ukraine; thus, concentrating the ethnic Minority (Russians) mainly in the Eastern part of Ukraine.

The words “*Ukrainian children*” could refer to individuals having Ukrainian citizenship, but are ethnic Russians. Owing to claim that Ukraine have estimated both the nationality and ethnicity of the children, then, it is direct and obvious question regarding the availability of DNA data on anonymous subjects (victims); furthermore, case-by-case. There should be both genomics and proteomics original measurands data on repository in addition to data on biological fluids and tissues; if any.

The Rome Statute does not indicate what standard of proof is to be applied in determining the reliability of the evidences. However, the proof must be established of guilt *beyond reasonable doubt* [General Comment B/21 UN Doc. A/39/40, pp. 143–147, §7]. The words «*reasonable doubt*» mean doubt found in reason. Therefore, the standard used to proof reliability of evidences regarding both the ethnicity and the nationality in addition to analysis of biological fluids and tissues in the context of documents falsifiability and reliability of genomics and proteomics data as well as their annotation; also, analytical data on biological fluids and tissues, in fact represent a chemometric tests. To some crucial methods used to fields of forensic research for legal purposes the author of the current contribution has methodological newcomers showing superior performances comparing with already practically implemented tools. The issue regarding scientific accuracy and legal accuracy of analytical data on a set of objects used to property of evidence is directly relevant to standards of proofs establishing the reliability of evidences, as well.

The emergence of novel scientific methodologies and methods does not just contribute to the fundamental knowledge, but also to the society, who first, describe and then advocate and propagate the novelty for various purposes of the economy and the human well-being. Thus, explicitly elaborated and proposed novel methods for the science in great detail is what the people take the scientific approach to be reliable; thus, allowing to add or even frequently replace the already accepted and established thinking. For the purposes of doing Justice the development of reliable approaches to the analytical chemometric data operating at the legal accuracy or reliability 100 % are crucial.

Such an argument is valid, because of open source evidences containing measurands and analytical data on biological samples of anonymous individuals including biological tissues and fluids does not contradict the **Rule 43**: (*Procedure applicable to the publication of documents of the Court*), which shall be discussed in a separate sub-section, below.

The seeking-truth *via* gathering of missive of data and information regarding particular crime and, thus, to build from these data together with other ones of associated crimes; if any, allow to reach the common belief as holding true statement. The massive of experiments are of significant importance to

be tackled reliably, because of if we observe a limited spatial-temporal scale of events /crimes around us, we are; thus, limiting the information we gather and process.

In other words, the wording of the AWT^[2] is complex not only, due to the fact that it includes hypothetical a large number of^[18] victims-children, or High State Public Elected Official; furthermore, of well-established and developed over Centuries social-policy system as is the Russian Federation's one, but also, primary, because of there is complex pre-history of the Ukraine-Russian conflict, which only approximately could be fixed on date 24.02.2022 as AWTs^[2] state. A detail looks at the near history of the Ukraine Russian relationships could be traced back formally in 1915 with the establishment of the Ukraine, however as aforementioned the novel self-governed area is characterized by a small number of only four regions. Currently, Ukraine is the largest territory among the Central and West European countries, and the whole Ukrainian history is only connected with the Russian Federation. Thus, this dramatic territorial expansion of Ukraine over the only 110 years needs an attention in connection with events, particularly, on 05.05.2014, when Ukrainian armed forces re-established control over towns in Donetsk and Luhansk Republics (p. 129^[32]); and 15.07.2014 when Ukrainian armed forces have started fighting on communication linking Luhansk with Russian border (p. 129^[32],) as well as heavy armed (Ukrainian) battalions and border guard units reinforced ca. 3000 fighters at about 150 km from Amvrosiivka and Izvaryne (p. 131^[32] (Izvaryne is Donetsk checkpoint with Russia.)

Therefore, hypothetic crimes^[18] processed in the AWTs^[2] are associated with very complex pre-history of these observed events and a long and broad spatial-temporal direction; thus, allowing altering of the objectivity of *doing Justice* due to a large number of radically polarized political views.

Any "Ukrainian estimates" regarding crimes of the Ukraine-Russian conflict as shown in work^[18]; for example, in terms evidences, facts, and arguments should be compulsory verified independently. This implies that evidences, particularly in the experimental analytical sciences and chemometrics should not be a simple matter of gathering data, but rather should involve design of additional experiments with testing of various established theories and innovations, as well. The latter assumes a partial open-source evidencing of the events tackled in AWTs^[2] (consider detail on, below).

In addition, the definition of '*mass crime*' involves evidences, facts and arguments regarding committed crimes involving minimum four (4) victims.

Further reaction against the obvious deficiency of clarity regarding the hypothetical victims^[18] of crimes called 'children' is connected with whom individuals are understood as 'children'? Why?

Looking at the texts of both the Article 50 and Article 77 the Fourth Geneva Convention of 1949 and its updates; for instance, Rules in the Additional Protocol I (Article 77), determining protection [of the children] against the effects of war [<https://ihl-databases.icrc.org/en/ihl-treaties/gciv-1949/article-50?activeTab=>], I should add that toward the children age, there should be make a comparative note with clause corresponds to similar provisions in some Penal Codes of States which is based on idea that an individual who has not reached the age of eighteen (18) years is not completely able to sound judgment. The subject does not always realize the significance of his, respectively, her actions and often acts under the influence of other individuals, if not under constraint^[20].

The latter paragraphs fix on problem with the AWTs^[2]-wording regarding the age groups of the children as potential victims of crimes. What there should be understood under '*children*'? Subjects up to 11-, 15- or 18-years old ones?

In order to avoid unnecessary complications, due to discuss Articles of numerous Conventions, Protocols and Statutes, I should mention that the maxim of *lex specialis* does not determine criteria to guide decision which area of the Law is more important than another one. The Convention [on Civil

and Political Rights] is applied also in situations of armed conflicts. Despite, the Rules of the International Humanitarian Law (IHL) are applicable to armed conflicts.

Thus, “*child*” is defined as in the Convention as “*every human being below the age of eighteen years unless under the law applicable to the child, majority is attained earlier*” (UN HRI/GEN/1/Rev.9 (Vol. II) 27.05.2008 [[https://docs.un.org/en/HRI/GEN/1/Rev.9\(Vol.II\)](https://docs.un.org/en/HRI/GEN/1/Rev.9(Vol.II))])

Particularly, more specific IHL-Rules may be especially relevant for interpreting Convention rights. Both the spheres of law are regarded as complementary and not mutually exclusive. In the cases of armed conflicts both the branches of international law *i.e.*, International Human Rights Law (IHRL) and IHL should be considered. See, for instance case Democratic Republic of the Congo v. Uganda, 2005 I.C.J. 116 (Dec. 19) §216 [<https://www.icj-cij.org/case/116>]. Thus, the remark on a lack of concreteness regarding the victims-children, including their ages in the AWTs^[2] is very important, as well.

Despite, looking at ECs^[13] of Article 6 of the Rome Statute^[1], there is written:

Article 6 (e) Genocide by forcibly transferring children

Elements

1. *The perpetrator forcibly transferred one or more persons.*
2. *Such person or persons belonged to a particular national, ethnical, racial or religious group.*
3. *The perpetrator intended to destroy, in whole or in part, that national, ethnical, racial or religious group, as such.*
4. *The transfer was from that group to another group.*
5. *The person or persons were under the age of 18 years.*
6. *The perpetrator knew, or should have known, that the person or persons were under the age of 18 years.*
7. *The conduct took place in the context of a manifest pattern of similar conduct directed against that group or was conduct that could itself effect such destruction.*

Thus, if we must have markers among various texts, if we are to be able to define the discussed children-victims^[18]; thus, interpreting the things we talk about, herein, then perhaps there should be understood that the children-victims are under 18 years old. The latter statement could be further argued looking at the text of Article 21(1)(a) of the Rome Statute^[1] stating that the Court shall apply: (a) *In the first place, this Statute, Elements of Crimes and its Rules of Procedure and Evidence.*

1.2. *On the Rule 43 of Procedure and Evidence; ‘International Military Conflict’; ‘Grave Crimes’; ‘State Party’; and State Party in conflict*

This sub-section, first focuses the reader attention on wording”*that the warrants are secret in order to protect victims...*”^[2(a)], which presumably should be much surely clear owing to Rule 43^[21]:

Rule 43: *Procedure applicable to the publication of documents of the Court*

The Court shall ensure that all documents subject to publication in accordance with the Statute and the Rules respect the duty to protect the confidentiality of the proceedings and the security of victims and witnesses.

However, there should be a trouble due to the following reasons:

- (i) The “*Civil society organisations*” have played a key role in advocating for *doing Justice* [<https://www.icc-cpi.int/get-involved/ngos>];
- (ii) The Trials are generally open to the public and visitors, who could attend them; furthermore, without prior registration [<https://www.icc-cpi.int/visit>];

(iii) According to the Universal Declaration of Human Rights [<https://www.un.org/en/about-us/universal-declaration-of-human-rights>], there is Article 19 stating:

Article 19

Everyone has the right to freedom of opinion and expression; this right includes freedom to hold opinions without interference and to seek, receive and impart information and ideas through any media and regardless of frontiers.

(iv) A draft of definition of the so-called open-source information states:

“Online open-source information is information that is publicly available on the internet. Open-source information may include (but is not limited to) that which is created, shared, or collated by journalists and news organizations; state agencies; political and military actors; commercial entities; international organizations; non-governmental and civil society organizations (NGOs); academics and academic institutions; private individuals; and groups of individuals with military, political, commercial, professional, and personal affiliations. Common types of online open-source information include online news articles; expert and NGO reports; social media content; image and sound recordings; geospatial imagery and mapping data; documents, including public administrative records and leaked confidential documents; library holdings, and more.”^[22].

The NGOs could participate into international criminal investigations (p. 19^[23]) in doing so-called digital open-source investigations. A particular remark on, herein, is the fact that the so-called “*evidence problem*” or ‘failure to investigate properly’ is broadly discussed in the literature. As sketched still in the Abstract section it involves also false documents, DNA-analyses, and other objects having property of physical evidences, among many other ones. Partially, a set of problems have been sketched^[24], as well. Due to a lack of sufficient evidences, there could be used including photographs from newspapers as property of physical evidence. If it is so, then, the lack of open-source information prevents involvement of; for instance, NGOs into digital open-source investigations.

In addition, explicitly Article 21(3) of the Rome Statute^[1] states that application and interpretation of law ‘*must be consistent with internationally recognized human rights*’.

Article 21

(3) The application and interpretation of law pursuant to this article must be consistent with internationally recognized human rights, and be without any adverse distinction founded on grounds such as gender as defined in article 7, paragraph 3, age, race, colour, language, religion or belief, political or other opinion, national, ethnic or social origin, wealth, birth or other status.

Dealing with AWTs^[2] of Publicly Elected High State Official, evidences, facts, and arguments; if any, exploited during the *do Justice* could be tackled within the more than one theory or law; thus, providing competitive explanation of observed facts compatible with evidences. The *politicide* is currently broadly implemented into debating crimes against individuals and social group people. Events in Eastern Ukraine (2013–2014) also indicate a strong policy motivation behind committed crimes against ethnic Russian Minority, particularly concentrating on crimes committed Odessa. Odessa, is Russian speaking city. The Donbass have shown until 30.09.2022 bilingual administrative systems. These events should be distinguished from Euro-Maidan movements (Kiev) dating on 21.11.2014. The latter movements are limited to short span of time 04.14–21.11.2014, despite, that they are also associated with escalation of conflict and committed crimes due to political reasons. The discussed armed operation by RA is initially connected with events of killing of ethnic Russians in Odessa (02.05.2014) where street deaths of dozens pro-Russian activists (p. 128^[9].) In total, 42 perished by fire in Odessa’s Trade-Union Building; 6 lost their lives in earlier clashes; and 208 – wounded^[25]. There are also ca. 13000 killed people from the Eastern Ukraine (2019 (?!)) until 24.02.2022^[9,12,18].

There are cases, so far, which have been regarded as ...” *political act and not aimed at establishing the truth*”. Consider, for instance^[26], among many other available references, including the cited in^[26] selected bibliography.

Regarding, point (iv), there could be further argued that the Human rights and the Universal Declaration of Human Rights underpin the Rome Statute including the exercise of *doing Justice*. The Rome Statute provisions must be interpreted and applied in accordance with internationally recognized human rights. First and foremost, in its context is right to a fair Trial^[27] ([ICC-01/04–01/06], [<https://www.icc-cpi.int/court-record/icc-01/04-01/06-803-ten>]; §37). The effort on securing victims and witnesses legally should not contradict the Articles protecting rights the **Subject 1**, as well.

(v) The interpretation and application of the European Convention on Human Rights to practices of the Transitional Justice highlight the following obligations: (a) *room must be left for free debate about the past (the freedom of expression to seek historical truth)*; and (b) **no amnesty must be granted for perpetrators of human rights violations, among others**^[28]. The seeking-truth, therefore, is the primary task in *doing Justice*. The formulation of belief as holding-true statements, however, request interpretation of evidences and facts.

(vi) Owing to the fact that in all cases, there is requested proof that underlying crime (*i.e.*, war crime, crimes against humanity or genocide) was committed, before the individual criminal responsibility (ICR) of the accused is considered, then all evidences of these 20000^[18] committed crimes should be available. All evidences; for instance, video records, analysis of biological samples, documents, *et cetera*, linking **Subject 1** with these hypotheticals 20000^[18] crimes, should be already collected and, thus, they should be provided publicly. Because of, neither open-source data on analyses of biological samples of anonymous victims, nor data on analyses of documents contradict the Rule 43, as highlighted before.

Owing to points (i)–(vi), there can be formulated a key problem (4):

Key problem (4): A lack of open-source evidences.

Further: Let us attempt to shed more light on the events over span of time 01.09.2014–24.02.2022. As the reader shall be convinced, these details are of crucial importance in tackling the AWTs^[2].

The classification of events associated with killing of more than 13000 civilians^[9] in Ukraine before date 24.02.2022 is highly doubtful. Are these cases of politicide, ethnic-cleaning, or genocide against ethnic Russians – it remains an open question. I am providing, herein, the definition of crime of genocide: ‘The denial of the existence of entire human groups’.

Conversely, crime of homicide is defined as: ‘The denial of the right to live of individual human beings^[29–31]’.

Thus, the distinction of ethnic groups, the citizenship, ethnic, and civil national identity of the victims within determined group individuals is crucial. The AWTs^[2] lacks of such as distinction of the victims.

Perhaps, there would be questions, why such timed-framework should be adopted looking at events happened before 01.09.2014 and events happened within the 01.09.2014–24.02.2022; and, why there should be categorized the killed group individuals within the Eastern Ukraine by the Ukrainian Executive Authorities or DNR-Oblast until 24.02.2022 as well as within the 17.05.2015–24.02.2022, when the discussed events are internal ones within the framework of Ukraine. Moreover, as aforementioned the conflict on 30.04.2014 has been already classified as non-international one^[32].

I shall attempt to address such questions; if any, in a following manner. The crimes, called '*Grave breaches*' of the Geneva Conventions are under Article 8(2)(a) of the *Rome Statute*^[RS].

It is not explicitly stated that Paragraph (a) treats only international armed conflicts. Perhaps, it should be understood in the context; thus, suggesting that Article 8(2)(a) treats only international military conflicts, but there is a lack of significant difference in wording between provisions of the ICTY Statute [https://www.icty.org/x/file/Legal%20Library/Statute/statute_sept09_en.pdf], the Roman Statute [<https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/2024-05/Rome-Statute-eng.pdf>], and the Geneva Conventions [<https://www.icrc.org/en/law-and-policy/geneva-conventions-and-their-commentaries>], among others.

Thus, I should emphasise that in cases ([IT-94-1]/14.07.1997); [<https://www.icty.org/en/case/tadic>], [<https://www.icty.org/x/cases/tadic/acjug/en/tad-aj990715e.pdf>], ([IT-96-21-T] Judgment, 16.11.1998, (1999) 38 ILM 57, §202], [https://www.icty.org/x/cases/mucic/tjug/en/981116_judg_en.pdf], and [(IT-95-14/1);§29–49], [<https://www.icty.org/en/case/aleksovski>] there has been applied description of '*Grave breaches*' as acts committed (herein, I have underlined the words *act* and *committed*) 'against persons or property protected under the provisions of the relevant Geneva Convention'. In the decision of [No. IT-94-1] the ICTY held that the grave breaches regime of prosecution of crimes is applied only to international armed conflicts, even though this has not been explicitly stated in the ICTY Statute as in the Rome Statute.

There is: '*...did find that grave breaches of the Geneva Conventions could only be committed in international armed conflicts...*'([IT-96-21-T] Judgment, 16.11.1998, (1999) 38 ILM 57, §202], [<https://www.icty.org/en/case/mucic>])

From the latter paragraph we understand that prosecution of *grave breaches* is carried out only in cases of international armed conflicts. Since, the conflicts in the territory of Ukraine is regarded as non-international one^[32], there is a lack of shown initiated investigation of *grave breaches* within the 01.09.2014–24.02.2022 (an almost 8 years period). If it is so, then the AWTs^[2] should fix '*since*' 24.02.2022?

Conversely, AWTs^[2] have used an indefinite temporal form '*at least*' date.

In parallel, UN Doc. A/BUR/50 (1946) [<https://digitallibrary.un.org/record/752074?v=pdf>] states: Whereas the punishment of the very serious crime of genocide when committed in time of peace lies within the exclusive territorial jurisdiction of the judiciary of every State concerned, while crimes of a relatively lesser importance such as piracy, trade in women, children, drugs, obscene publications are declared as international crimes and have been *made matters of international concern*.

Therefore, the issue regarding initiated investigations of '*Grave breaches*' within the 01.09.2014–24.02.2022 in the AWTs-wording^[2] is crucial. Because of, there is also Article 15 (1)^[1] (*proprio motu*), allowing to do so. Furthermore, there is a lack of hierarchy among various crimes under Articles 6, Article 7, and Article 8 of the Rome Statute^[1].

Why do I focus the reader's attention on a parallel considering Article 6^[1], Article 7^[1], and Article 8^[1], despite the fact that the AWTs^[2] show Article 8^[1]? As aforementioned, the Rome Statute does not imply a formal hierarchy among war crimes, crimes against humanity, and genocide, in spite of that Article 21(3)^[1] has hierarchically lower legal status compare with Article 21(2)^[1] one.

The Article 7^[1], therefore, has not hierarchically high legal status toward Article 8^[1]. There is no formal hierarchy for Article 6^[1], although genocide is considered as the Crime above all other crimes in terms of gravity according to International Criminal Tribunal for Rwanda (ICTR) ([ICTR-97-23-S/04.09.1998]

[<https://www.refworld.org/jurisprudence/caselaw/ictr/1998/en/38168>] and [ICTR-98-39-S/05.02.1999] [<https://www.refworld.org/jurisprudence/caselaw/ictr/1999/en/64146>].

The 'War crime' (under Article 8^[1]) address criminal conduct (act) of a perpetrator (individual) towards an immediate protected subject, while Rules proscribing crimes against humanity (under Article 7^[1]) address perpetrator's conduct (again, committed crime by individual) not only towards the immediate victim, but also toward the whole of humankind. Crimes against humanity are particularly odious forms of misbehaviour. They, further, should form part of a widespread and systematic practice or policy. Due to their heinousness and magnitude the crimes against humanity constitute egregious attacks on human dignity, on the very notion of humaneness. The crimes consequently affect, or should affect, each and every human, whatever his, respectively, her nationality, ethnicity, and population location ([IT-96-22-A/7.10.1997], [<https://www.icty.org/x/cases/erdemovic/acjug/en/erd-aj971007e.pdf>]].)

Both the Article 7^[1] and Article 8^[2] detail on crimes *deportation or forcible transfer of population* (see Article 7(1)(d)^[1]), *unlawful deportation or transfer or unlawful confinement* (Article 8(2)(a)(vii)^[1]), and *the transfer, directly or indirectly, by the Occupying Power of parts of its own civilian population into the territory it occupies, or the deportation or transfer of all or parts of the population of the occupied territory within or outside this territory*" (Article 8(2)(b)(viii)^[1]).

According to AWTs^[2] issued against **Subject 1** as a hypothetical perpetrator (individual committed crimes in term of *actus reus*), as aforementioned, he presumably has committed a specific crime against each victim as an individual.

Therefore, if there is assumed that AWTs^[2] refer to, in total 20000 children^[18], then this means that the individual **Subject 1** has committed 20000 crimes. The investigation is case-by-case (below). Is it possible that he, alone, did this to each of these children, factually and physically? Absurd!

Is it physically possible **Subject 1** and **Subject 2** to commit 20000 conducts as Joint Criminal Enterprise (JCE) of two individuals? Again, absurd!

The lack of hierarchy of the legal status of Article 6^[1], Article 7^[1] and Article 8^[1], however, gives rise to the so-called *re-categorization* of crime during a Trial, again involving **Subject 1**, but with charges under Article 7^[1].

Crimes against humanity, insofar as they are not related to the Laws of War, but rather to Human Rights Law and are; thus, equally categorizing as mass acts against human rights, can also be attributed to him for crimes «deportation» and forcible «transfer» of children who are not from areas of direct conflict or those who are not from directly occupied areas of the Russian Federation, as well as those who were "deported" before the conduct of hostilities.

Therefore, how should be charged an accused depends rather primary from number of victims, but not only. Due to this reason, the relationship between crimes against humanity and the laws of war is more complex than those dealing with human rights. Particular, examples from the practice should be provided, below.

At this point, I should stress on the following facts. Within the 01.09.2014–24.02.2022 of ca. 8 years there is a lack of investigations of *grave breaches* or there are investigations, but there is a lack of crimes tackled in AWTs^[2] until a short span of time, perhaps, 'at least 24.02.2022', when there are generated at about 20000 crimes^[18]. Doubtful! If there were committed crimes, then why the AWTs^[2] appears on 17.03.2023 – or at about 10 years as duration of time? Conversely, if there is a lack of crimes, then, why there is written 'at least' instead of 'since' date in the AWT^[2]. Does it mean that there

is further shifting of the nature of the Ukraine-Russian conflict within the 24.02.2022–2023? It remains also an open question.

In cases of hypothetical 20000^[18] crimes against children who should presumably be deported or transferred forcibly from Ukraine or DNR Oblast within the 17.05.2015–30.09.2022 where not all of the territory is occupied by hostilities assumes a spatial-temporal distinguishing of all these cases. Because, these details prove to be crucial in defining the ECs of deportation and forcible ‘transfer. There are so-called *State Party in the conflict* with effective control over a deportation zone; the so-called ‘*Occupying Power*; the presence or a lack of hostilities in the location from which the deportation, respectively, transfer took place; whether the deportation, respectively, transfer was preceded by hostilities, *etc.*

Despite, a lack of open source evidences, there should be 20000^[18] different cases of alleged child abductions which are attributed according to wording of the AWTs^[2] as a single act conducted by a single individual (**Subject 1**) (only); furthermore, who has never even seen these children.

Owing to the lack of inter-Article hierarchy of the legal status of the discussed Article 7^[1] and Article 8^[1], I should add, herein that the application of Article 6^[1] with respect to ECs refers to “Notwithstanding the normal requirement for a mental element provided for in Article 30^[1], and recognizing that knowledge of the circumstances will usually be addressed in proving genocidal intent, the appropriate requirement, if any, for a mental element regarding this circumstance will need to be decided by the Court on a case-by-case basis”.

On the other hand, Article 6 (e) states again: ‘*by forcibly transferring children*’.... The term ‘*forcibly*’ is not restricted to physical force, but may include threat of force or coercion, such as that caused by fear of violence, duress, detention, psychological oppression or abuse of power, against such person or persons or another person, or by taking advantage of a coercive environment.

In all likelihood, they were not even deported or removed from the same place at the same time. However, when categorizing the crime of deportation (under Article 7^[1] or Article 8^[2]) which is done regardless of how the charge is brought, there is also determined the State Party in the conflict exercising effective administrative control over the area from which the civilians [children in this case] were deported or re-located, in addition to so-called *occupied territory*.

The Article 6^[1], Article 7^[1], Article 8^[1] have highlighted the word ‘*Perpetrator*’ as individual committed crimes, respectively presented in the crime scene during the committed crime. The same is valid to the texts defining the ECs as shown in the case of Article 6(e), above.

Therefore, despite the categorization of a crime, the addressat (BG: адресат; ENG: addressee or recipient) is primary the perpetrator of the crime or the individual conducting the conduct (*actus reus*). As I have written before, **Subject 1** physically unable to conduct 20000^[18] acts of deportation or transfer of 20000 individuals, even children; furthermore, from various categories areas of military conflict as sketched, above.

In order to convince the reader regarding the reliability of my statement that **Subject 1** is involved as innocence individual into a large-scale event^[18] according to AWTs^[2], I shall further support my statements with more real cases of the ICTs practice, so far, dealing with crimes committed armed conflicts. Because of, it is plausible to argue that most of our knowledge of matter of facts is directly based on experience.

Thus, case [IT-06-90-PT/19.03.2007], [<https://www.icty.org/x/cases/gotovina/custom3/en/pros-ptb.pdf>] has found that deportation as a crime against humanity has not been limited to occupied territory, as

required by the laws of war. Therefore, it cannot be treated under the laws of war (or Article 8^[1].) in its entirety. Such an act of deportation is treated under Article 7^[1] (crime against humanity), which as we have said is related to re-categorization of the crime. Case [IT-06-90-PT/19.03.2007][<https://www.icty.org/x/cases/gotovina/custom3/en/pros-ptb.pdf>], also argued that distinction between deportation and the laws of war is not entirely consistent with regard to relation between crimes against humanity and the laws of war. There is a casual tendency to view these two categories as completely separate and independent categories; thus, justifying expansive interpretations of crimes against humanity regardless of requirements of humanitarian law. Despite, that there is a distinction by Articles 7^[1] and 8^[1] of the Charter (UN-TS/2187/38544/01.06.2002) it is very elusive. It states:

"[t]erritory is considered occupied when it is actually placed under the authority of the enemy army. Occupation extends only to the territory where such an authority is established and can exercise control."

A question has been raised during the above case, whether the elements of deportation or forcible transfer were different when the charge was brought as crimes against humanity rather than as war crimes. The indictment alleged that military actions prior to occupation had displaced all, but a "small part" of the civilian population. That is, the limitation of charges of deportation as a crime against humanity from unoccupied to occupied territory defined two categories of deportees – from occupied territory and from territory that was about to be occupied. This categorization is, in addition to the categorization according to «deportation from a zone of effective military operations» and «deportation from a zone where there are no military operations», which I wrote about above.

As a form of pro-argument regarding my statements above, we should return to AWTs^[2]; thus, arguing the following on the base on case [IT-06-90-PT/19.03.2007]. If **Subject 1** has committed crimes of deportation or transfer of children, then, physically he should be presented in at about 20000^[18] crime scenes; furthermore, in inoccupied or occupied territories or territory that was about to be occupied in addition to zone where there are or no military operations.

A case in which, regardless of how the charge was brought, an investigation has been made of whether the crime of deportation could be categorized as a crime against humanity or a war crime, was case [IT-97-25-A/17.09.2003], [<https://www.refworld.org/jurisprudence/caselaw/icty/2003/en/34902>], as well. It was held that the content of the crime deportation did not differ whether it was committed as a war crime or as a crime against humanity.

Regarding, cases [IT-06-90-PT/19.03.2007], [<https://www.icty.org/x/cases/gotovina/custom3/en/pros-ptb.pdf>] and [IT-97-25-A/17.09.2003], [<https://www.refworld.org/jurisprudence/caselaw/icty/2003/en/34902>], there has been highlighted that they details individual guilt, although not comprehensively, but they do not address the State Party in armed conflicts and related war crimes.

Owing to the fact that there is not much significant difference among texts of ICTY Statute [https://www.icty.org/x/file/Legal%20Library/Statute/statute_sept09_en.pdf], the Roman Statute [<https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/2024-05/Rome-Statute-eng.pdf>], and the Geneva Conventions [<https://www.icrc.org/en/law-and-policy/geneva-conventions-and-their-commentaries>], at this point I should stress that case [IT-06-90-PT/19.03.2007] [<https://www.icty.org/x/cases/gotovina/custom3/en/pros-ptb.pdf>] states:

..."Under the laws of war, the crime of deportation is part of the Geneva Convention and therefore applies only to civilians "in the hands" of a party to the conflict"....

Focusing the reader's attention on the latter statement, it becomes clear that the Geneva Conventions should be applied to treat civilians, including children. If it is so, then, Article 50 already detailed above obligates to protect children from effect of war, compulsory.

Essentially, this classifies the Russian Army's military operation since 24.02.2022 in DNR-Oblast and Ukraine as *humanitarian intervention*, as has been, already highlighted above; and, as the discussed case illustrates, such classification appears justifiable within the commonly accepted by ICTs understanding of the Geneva Conventions.

The case [IT-06-90-PT/19.03.2007] statement shown above also indicates that even if there is not addressed actions of State Party in committing a crime, it is not excluded as a party to a criminal case.

In the context of the *State responsibility*, it should be noted that genocide, particularly, is classified as international crime, for commission of which principals and accessories as well as States are individually responsible (UN A/BUR/50 [<https://digitallibrary.un.org/record/752074?v=pdf>]). If there is a lack of formal hierarchy among the Article 6^[1], Article 7^[1] and Article 8^[1], then the latter text assumes that the "State" could be also implement into responsibility for 'war crimes' or 'crimes against humanity'. Such text lacks of the AWTs^[2], however.

Due to the latter reason, there is defined **key problem (5)**.

Key problem (5): AWTs^[2] wording lacks of defined State Party in conflict Ukraine, State Party Russia in conflict, and Oblast Party Donetsk People's Republic in the conflict within the 17.05.2015–30.09.2022.

Due to SOFA Agreement [https://web.archive.org/web/20140321072522/http://www.mid.ru/bdomp/spd_md.nsf/0/BBC88CF0F9DF3F9F44257C9800383F4D] the presence of the Russian Army on the territory of Ukraine within the 12.07.1999–24.02.2022 does not make the Russian Federation a State Party in a conflict neither with Ukraine nor with Donetsk People's Republic (Oblast) (17.05.2015–30.09.2022).

Regarding, **key problem (5)** and tackling a lack of defined, *State Party in context conflict*, I should underline that, despite, that Ukraine is not State Party of the Rome Statute, there are complaints by Ukraine and declarations lodged by Government of Ukraine on; for instance, 17.04.2014 and 8.09.2015; thus, allowing an exercising jurisdiction over *Rome Statute* regarding crimes committed on the territory of Ukraine from 21.11.2013 onwards (consider, Report on Preliminary Examination Activities 2017; p. 83 [https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/itemsDocuments/2017-PE-rep/2017-otp-rep-PE_ENG.pdf]).

The change of statute of Donetsk People's Republic as Oblast, having Special Statute since 17.05.2015, assumes that this territory is excluded from exercising jurisdiction in DNR-Oblast; thus, presumably restricting investigations within the 21.11.2013-17.05.2015. If it is so, *i.e.*, that the AWTs^[2] accept Minsk II Agreement, then there is further argument regarding the classification of the conflict in DNR Oblast within the period 17.05.2015–30.09.2022 as international military conflict, but between Ukraine and DNR-Oblast.

If, there is investigated within the territory of DNR Oblast after 17.05.2015, then it should mean that (i) the AWTs^[2] do not accept the Minsk II Agreement. If it is so, then there explicitly should be written criteria on acceptance.

If, there is investigated crimes after 17.05.2015 and AWTs^[2] accept the Minsk II Agreements, then this should mean that there is determined DNR-Oblast as Oblast Party in the conflict.

The latter fact; if any, again focuses on the AWTs^[2] showing only... "in Ukraine", but not "in Donetsk People's Republic Oblast (17.05.2015–24.02.2022).

With **key problem (5)**, among others, I strongly hope that the interested reader should further convince himself, respectively, herself that the lack of an exact spatial-temporal determination of the various crimes case-by-case; if any, *per* span of time and territory depending on a strict list of International Agreements between Ukraine and Russia as well other States, which AWTs^[2] accepts, respectively, reject, makes AWTs^[2] highly questionable, disputable, ambiguous, and doubtful, respectively.

Further: It is emphasized, that whether victims are among the protected population under the Geneva Convention depends on when they fell into the hands of the so-called occupying forces. The exact moment (date, time) when an (civilian) individual (or child) or an area falls into the hands of a party to the conflict depends on the extent to which that State party in the conflict has effective control over the area (see case [IT-94-1]/14.07.1997, [<https://www.icty.org/en/case/tadic>]).

In other words, due to assumed large scale of victims of deportation or forcible transfer, *i.e.*, ca. 20000^[18] children, a re-categorization of the crime can result in one act being lawful while another act being unlawful simply by changing the category crime from 'War crimes' (Article 8^[1]) to 'Crimes against humanity' (Article 7^[1]) solely on the basis of the arguments and opinions set out above.

Importantly, case [IT-95-14-//03.03.2000], [<https://www.icty.org/en/case/blaskic>] has been ruled in accordance with previous decisions and convictions. Explicitly, Article 21(2)^[1] of the Rome Statute^[1] states that: "*The Court may apply principles and rules of law as interpreted in its previous decisions*".

In addition to an armed conflict, it is imperative to find a clear link between the alleged crimes and the armed conflict as a whole. This does not mean that all the crimes must have been committed in the exact geographical region where an armed conflict is taking place at a given span of time. To show that a link exists, it is sufficient that, the alleged crimes are closely linked to ongoing hostilities in other parts of the territories controlled by the parties to the conflict. This means that a given municipality needs not to be the victim of an armed confrontation for IHL to apply there.

Cases [IT-94-1], [<https://www.icty.org/en/case/tadic>] and [IT-96-21-A/20.01.2001], [<https://www.icty.org/x/cases/mucic/acjug/en/cel-aj010220.pdf>]) state that the crime must not be part of a policy or practice officially approved or tolerated by one of parties to conflict or that the act is in actual implementation of a policy related to conduct of war or in the actual interest of a party to the conflict.

It can be seen from the above that there must be a sufficient connection between the criminal act and the armed conflict. If the relevant crime was committed in the course of a battle or the capture of a city, for example, this would make the crime a war crime case [IT-95-14-T, §69] [<https://www.refworld.org/jurisprudence/caselaw/icty/2000/en/19490>]).

Such a direct connection with actual military action is not required in every situation, however. In the decisions rendered so far, the *ad hoc* IMTs have used an objective test to determine the existence and nature of an armed conflict, as well as connection with conflict. With regard to this element, the ICTs have never required a mental element (*mens rea*) connected with it.

The definition of "*international armed conflict*" has been established as follows:

"...an international armed conflict exists whenever there is a resort to armed force between States..." (case [IT-94-1-AR72]§ 70 [

AR72%29%20ICTY.pdf]; International Law Reports, Vol. 105 ILR pp. 453–488 [http://dx.doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781316152348.004].)

The definition of "*international armed conflict*" has been further developed:

"[a]ny difference arising between two States and leading to the intervention of members of the armed forces" is an international armed conflict and..." (case [IT-96-21-T/16.11.1998], §208 [https://www.icty.org/x/cases/mucic/tjug/en/981116_judg_en.pdf].)

The case [IT-94-1-AR72][https://m.asylumlawdatabase.eu/sites/default/files/aldfiles/Prosecutor%20v%20Tadic%20%28IT-94-1-AR72%29%20ICTY.pdf] also raised the question regarding conditions under which an armed conflict within the borders of a State can be qualified as *international armed conflict* when other States intervene in that conflict. There has been ruled...that an armed conflict is international if it is between two or more States (...*It is indisputable that an armed conflict is international if it takes place between two or more States...*).

Clearly, the term '*international armed conflict*' includes military occupations.

In a case of an internal armed conflict that has broken out within the territory of a State, it may also give rise to an international conflict depending on circumstances, with an international conflict being alongside an internal armed conflict. An internal conflict may also escalate into an international one. An international conflict is defined by (i) the intervention of another State in an internal conflict through its troops or if (ii) some of the actors in the internal armed conflict act on behalf of another State (case [IT-94-1-A/15.07.1999,§84] [https://www.icty.org/x/cases/tadic/acjug/en/tad-aj990715e.pdf]).

The latter paragraph aims at again highlighting the lack of investigation in territory of DNR Oblast within 17.05.2015–24.02.2022 owing to the fact that according to the Rome Statute there is (Article 15 (1)^[1] *proprio motu*) regarding the well-documented committed crimes within the period 01.09.2014–24.02.2022 in DNR Oblast despite how there should be classified the conflict.

A latter note regarding Article 15 (1) of the Rome Statute is according to the following statement:

... *Crimes against humanity are aimed at any civilian population and are prohibited regardless of whether they are committed in an armed conflict, international or internal in character...* (case [IT-95-14-T/03.03.2000], §67 [https://www.refworld.org/jurisprudence/caselaw/icty/2000/en/19490]).

Is there assumed that there are carried out investigations involving DNR Oblast, as well as since 21.10.2013 according p. 83 (Report on Preliminary Examination Activities 2017; p. 83 [https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/itemsDocuments/2017-PE-rep/2017-otp-rep-PE_ENG.pdf]), then the AWTs^[2] date is 17.10.2023 or is a time duration of investigation of ca. 10 years (21.10.2013–17.03.23).

From the perspective of Russian Federation as Party State in the Ukraine-Russia conflict, I have laid the period (21.10.2013 (?)) 17.05.2015–24.02.2022 peacetime (**Figure 3**). The latter formulation is agreed with the legal practice tackling the Crimes under Article 6^[1] as an offence that could be committed in time of peace as well as in wartime. The major motivation behind this temporal distinction of crimes between committed during wartime or peace time has been that there were several variants on the definition of crimes against humanity, some of them eliminating the nexus with armed conflict (Agreement for the Prosecution and Punishment of Major War Criminals of the European Axis, and Establishing the Charter of the International Military Tribunal (IMT), Annex, (1951) 82; [https://www.refworld.org/legal/agreements/un/1945/en/56517]).

Despite, doubt regarding classification the Ukraine-DNR conflict within the 17.05.2015–30.09.2022 and participation of the Ukraine and DNR Oblast as Party State, respectively, Party Oblast in Ukraine and Oblast DNR in the conflict, it is sharply distinguished from phase of conflict since 24.02.2022 when there is *humanitarian intervention* of the Army of Russia in the territory of DNR Oblast.

Further, we shall look at the essence of the discussed AWTs^[2] and definitions of crimes under Article 8^[1] and how they should be understood from perspective of the legal terms. In addition, I shall seek to show how they are already applied to practice of ICTs.

1.3. Deportation and forcible transfer of populations [children in this case]; State responsibility

To begin with, **Article 8 (2)**^[1] states:

Article 8 (War crimes)

2. For the purpose of this Statute, "war crimes" means:

a) **Grave breaches** of the **Geneva Conventions of 12 August 1949**, namely, any of the following acts against persons or property protected under the provisions of the relevant Geneva Convention

(vii) Unlawful deportation or transfer or unlawful confinement;

Article 8 (War Crimes)

2. For the purpose of this Statute, "war crimes" means:

(b) Other serious violations of the laws and customs applicable in international armed conflict, within the established framework of international law, namely, any of the following acts:

(viii) The transfer, directly or indirectly, by the Occupying Power of parts of its own civilian population into the territory it occupies, or the **deportation or transfer** of all or parts of the population of the occupied territory within or outside this territory.

The obvious point would be the categorization of the crimes; if any, as *War crimes*.

First, and foremost, the 'War Crime' is conduct type crime! However, there is distinction between war crimes and ordinary criminal behaviour. In the former case there is established link between the offences and the armed conflict. crimes unrelated to an armed conflict; for instance, murder for personal reasons are not considered to be war crimes.

The Rome Statute does not define the term 'conduct'. The same is true for 'circumstance' or 'consequence'. Instead of, there are three types of material elements (*actus reus*).

However, there are conduct elements including 'a prohibited action or prohibited omission. They are described in the definition of a crime. The consequence elements referring either to a completed result; or the creation of a state of harm or risk of harm; for instance. The circumstance elements qualify the conduct and consequences and are associated with things mentioned in the conduct and consequence elements.

Due to these reasons, when there is referred, herein, conduct, then, it should be highlighted both the act of crime or omission.

Preliminary, I would like to mention that the Commentary on Rome Statute broadly highlight that the dividing line among the various type of material elements is not always clear. The major concerns refer to the fact that the *actus reus* of a crime is classified primary as conduct (below) elements. However, they actually describe results due to the act. Therefore, they should be treated as consequence elements. In other words, there is crime, when the result of the crime is observed and experienced. For instance, there is crime of homicide, when there is observed and established physically and really the death of a human.

Thus, under the legal term *war crime*, there is understood: 'violations of the laws or customs of war. Such violations shall include, but not be limited to, murder, ill-treatment or deportation to slave labour or for any other purpose of civilian population of or in occupied territory, murder or ill-treatment of prisoners of war or persons on the seas, killing of hostages, plunder of public or private property, wanton destruction of cities, towns or villages, or devastation not justified by military necessity^[33]'.

Next there is stated the Geneva Convention (Article 8(2)(a))^[1]. However, the Conventions only covered what is known as 'Geneva law', addressing the protection of victims of armed conflict. Despite, as aforementioned in cases of children, there is Article 50 (protection of children).

Therefore, there should be sharply distinguished between deportation of children and deportation of civilian population. In this case, there is not challenge to introduce the Article 50, because of it obligates to protect children from the effect of war. Thus, AWTs^[2] have no reason to equalize the children with civilian population, when the children are specially protected group individuals within the Article 50.

Furthermore, the word deportation is used to purpose; for instance, slave labour or relevant ones. In this context, if there is concentrated on ECs of Article 7(1)(c) (crime against humanity of enslavement), then there is:

1. The perpetrator exercised any or all of the powers attaching to the right of ownership over one or more persons, such as by purchasing, selling, lending or bartering such a person or persons, or by imposing on them a similar deprivation of liberty.

It is understood that such deprivation of liberty may, in some circumstances, include exacting forced labor or otherwise reducing a person to a servile status as defined in the Supplementary Convention on the Abolition of Slavery, the Slave Trade, and Institutions and Practices Similar to Slavery of 1956. It is also understood that the conduct described in this element includes trafficking in persons, in particular women and children.

Toward the so-called ‘transfer’ of population (Article 8(2)(b)(viii)^[1]) there is reflected in mind ‘*forcible transfer*’. The notion of *forcible transfer of populations* as generic legal term is applied to tackle an unlawful approach to, or policy of compelling people to leave their territory. However, it is applied chiefly in the context of transforming the demographic population composition. In addition, it is used to determine the political status of a territory.

“There is crime of “Deportation” when a perpetrator – herein, I particularly highlight the word ‘perpetrator’ (singular form) – deported or forcibly transferred, without grounds permitted under international law, one or more persons to another State or location, by expulsion or other coercive acts”.

However, namely Article 50 obligates to protect children from the effect of war. Thus, AWTs^[2], in fact, equalize the evacuation of children from a territory of armed conflict according to Article 50 to deportation and transfer of children; thus, categorizing the evacuation of children during international armed conflict as crime.

Further: There are broadly used two requirements for the discussed crime, *i.e.* forcible displacement and coercive acts; if any.

Particularly, talking about forcible child transfer there is further stated that the clause prohibits “*transferring children of the group to another group with intent to destroy national, religious, racial and ethnic groups in whole or in part.*”

“The nationality of victims for the purpose of the application of Geneva Convention IV should not be determined on the basis of formal national characteristics, but rather by an analysis of the substantive relations, taking into account the different ethnic origins of the victims and perpetrators and their links with the foreign intervening State” ([IT-95-14-T] §§ 126, 145; [<https://www.icty.org/en/case/blaskic>]; 122 ILR 1 at 58, 63. 32).

Owing to the cited data above and regarding the heterogeneous distribution of the at about 51.1–22 % ethnic Russian mainly within the Eastern part of Ukraine and DNR Oblast; and, at about more than 98 % ethnic Russian occupying the territory of Donbass, there is unable to carry out ethnic distinction between the so-called «*Occupying Power*» in the context of the Article 8^[1] which should be presumably the Russian Army, and the so-called victims-children from the Eastern territory of Ukraine, respectively, particularly, highlighting Donbass, and DNR Oblast within the 17.05.2015–30.09.2022 which should be mainly ethnic Russians. It is obvious that explicit spatial-temporal framework of the discussed (hypothetical) victims and hypothetical crimes should be fixed tackling this issue, as well.

In the context of the latter formulated problem, there should be noted that International Humanitarian Law is applied from the initiation of the armed conflicts and extends beyond the cessation of hostilities until a general conclusion of peace is reached ([IT-94-1-AR72] §70; [<https://m.asylumlawdatabase.eu/sites/default/files/aldfiles/Prosecutor%20v%20Tadic%20%28IT-94-1-AR72%29%20ICTY.pdf>]; 105 ILR 453 at 488) and that at least some of the provisions of the [Geneva] Conventions apply to the entire territory of the Parties to the conflict, not just the vicinity of actual hostilities...[P]articularly those relating to the protection of prisoners of war and civilians are not so limited [IT-94-1-AR72,§68].

In tackling the issue of application of Article 50 to protect children from the effect of war by the Russian Army or Russian State Border Authorities, the latter paragraph sheds important light that the Article 50 is in fact applicable in the entire territory of Ukraine and does not depend on the location of the actual hostilities. If it is, the so, that transfer of children from the Russian Executive Authorities; if any, as an attempt to protect them from the effect of war, due to significant dynamics of the events cannot be regarded as 'forcible transfer. Generally, such act; if any, is not crime. As aforementioned, the evacuation cannot be equalized to crime in the discussed case.

Regarding, territory under *effective control*, there should be also added that Case-law stretching from the European case gives strong support for obligations within the human rights law which can be extend to areas under effective control of the State. Occupied territories over which authority has been clearly established can come within the ambit of the human rights obligations of the State (see *Preliminary Objections*, 40/1993/ 435/514, §§62–64 [<https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng#%22itemid%22:%22001-58007%22>]); (*European Court of Human Rights (Application No 55721/07) Judgment of 7 July 2011*) [<https://www6.austlii.edu.au/au/journals/AUIntLawJI/2012/16.pdf>].

Thus, the human rights obligations could be extended extraterritorially. There is, however, disagreement, regarding the actual obligations:

- (i) toward "effective control" in occupation there may be a problem in areas where hostilities continue;
- (ii) there are debates on what constitutes control (e.g., whether there is a difference between ground troops or air power, and whether control over the consequences for the individual is enough without control over the territory), and the particular difficulties of regional systems covering situations outside the region; and
- (iii) toward the formulation of "within the power". It might well be argued that the obligations probably do not extend to extraterritorial battlefield conduct, but do exist once people have been removed from the battlefield and placed in a detention facility run by the State — though where the obligations begin along the line between the two is unclear (see Case No. 52207/99, 12 December 2001 [<https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng#%22itemid%22:%22001-22099%22>])).

There should be further accounted for that the legal term *forcibly* is not restricted only to physical force. It may include any act consisting of "*threats, threats of force, inflicted trauma, or coercion such as those caused by fear of violence, duress, detention, psychological oppression, abuse of power or by taking advantage of a coercive environment which would lead to the forcible transfer of children from one group to another*". The latter description of the discussed crimes is particularly taken from: [IT-98-33], 2.08.2001, §521 [<https://www.icty.org/en/case/krstic>]. According to Judgement, the legal terms 'deportation' and 'forcible transfer' required for a case of deportation – transfer beyond state borders. Conversely, the term 'forcible transfer' is applied to displace population, but within the framework of a state.

Case [IT-98-33, 2.08.2001], [<https://www.icty.org/en/case/krstic>] states: "...both deportation and forcible transfer relate to the involuntary and unlawful evacuation of individuals from the territory in which they reside. Yet, the two are not synonymous in customary international law. Deportation

presumes transfer beyond State borders, whereas forcible transfer relates to displacements within a State”.

In the latter case, there is certain kind of similarity with the AWTs^[2]-wording in equalizing the evacuation to crime, when it is unlawful. It also highlights the definition of the State border. Given that, and considering the provisions in Penal Codes of States regarding mental ability of individuals under eighteen (18) years old, who, presumably, are not completely able to sound judgment, as sub-section 1.1 already highlighted, then it became clear that such individuals should not be completely able to assess the effect of the war. Therefore, the term *unlawful evacuation* is obviously inapplicable to cases of evacuation of children.

The case [IT-97-25-T/15.03.2002], [https://www.refworld.org/jurisprudence/caselaw/icty/2002/en/19276] also held that the deportation is associated with displacement of persons across a national border. It has also distinguished between deportation and forcible transfer. The latter act; if any, takes place within national borders.

The issue of national border, which must be crossed for cases of deportation has been detailed on case [IT-97-24-T/31.07.2003], [https://www.refworld.org/jurisprudence/caselaw/icty/2003/en/40192], as well. The Article 5(d) of the ICTY Statute must be read to encompass forced displacements of population both the across internationally recognised borders and de facto boundaries, however, such as constantly changing frontlines, which are not internationally recognised. Thus, the definition of deportation of persons must include expulsion from an area in which they are lawfully present to an area under the control of another party. It is also stated that ECs emphasised that the first element of forcible transfer and deportation as crimes against humanity is that the victims were deported or forcibly transferred to another state or location.

Particularly, case [IT-97-24-T/31.07.2003], [https://www.refworld.org/jurisprudence/caselaw/icty/2003/en/40192] is plausible as an account of the application of terms deportation, forcible transfer, and evacuation to events committed on the Ukraine–DNR (Oblast) border within 17.05.2015–30.09.2022; if any. They are sharply distinguished from events committed in the Ukraine-Russia State Border; if any. Despite the fact, that such as spatial-temporal distinction is complicated, it precisely tackles both the State and Executive Power Authority responsibility regarding control over (state) border *per* State and Oblast depending on the span of time under discussion (below.) The latter case is the only one in which transfer across national borders is not tackled as an obligation of the crime of deportation. In the Rome Statute, the terms deportation and forcible transfer appear to be given the same meaning under Article 7(2)(d)^[1]. Thus, in cases of deportation and forcible transfer, the Rome Statute does not require proof of crossing of an international border, but only that a civilian population has been displaced. The Customary International Law, however, has long penalized forcible population displacements. The fact that the Rome Statute has adopted the two terms deportation and forcible transfer in the same category crime only reinforces the view-statement, that what is regarded to be two separate crimes is in fact, in reality the same crime.

Some Commentary of the Rome Statute detailing on crime against humanity of deportation claims that it is applied regardless of the purpose of the deportation and takes the view that the application of the Rome Statute uses a common distinction between crime deportation, as involving cross-border transfer. Conversely, the crime forcible transfer is related to movement within a determined territory. The view-statement is that the distinction between the discussed crimes is intended. Further, Commentaries of the latter issue tackling the ECs of deportation and forcible transfer under the Rome Statute insist upon intended distinction between the two crimes, as well.

Despite, forcible transfer of population is alternative crime to deportation, which encompass large-scale movements within a state’s borders. Therefore, the crime deportation should insist upon conduct across in the state’s border.

Case [IT-95-9], [<https://www.icty.org/en/case/simic>] has established that in cases of deportation under Article 5 of the ICTY Statute, the crossing of a national border must be proved. There is statement that the European Union (EU) have recognised Bosnia and Herzegovina as an independent state on 06.04.1992. Therefore, the transfer of population across Bosnia and Herzegovina's borders after this date satisfied the obligation of proof of crossing a national border.

If, it is so, then case [IT-95-9], [<https://www.icty.org/en/case/simic>] agrees with my statement that the DNR-Oblast within the span of time 17.05.2015–30.09.2022 should be regarded as internationally recognized self-governed Oblast with Special Statute.

Further: There is a frequently found view that a combination of wording 'deportation' and 'forcible transfer of population' refers to so-called '*ethnic cleansing*'. This is often case when there is ethnic-cleaning within a country's own borders. Numerous documents detail on legal application of the discussed crimes, particularly, looking at case [IT-94-1-AR72] (<https://m.asylumlawdatabase.eu/sites/default/files/aldfiles/Prosecutor%20v%20Tadic%20%28IT-94-1-AR72%29%20ICTY.pdf>]; Decision on the Defence Motion for Interlocutory Appeal on Jurisdiction, 2 October 1995, (1997) International Law Reports, Vol. 105 ILR p. 453 [CL-0519; https://icsid.worldbank.org/sites/default/files/parties_publications/C8394/Claimants%27%20documents/CL%20-%20Exhibits/CL-0519.pdf].)

Perhaps, the reader should not immediately infer why I use often the latter case, *i.e.*, [IT-94-1-AR72] in my interpretation of the AWTs^[2]-wording? There are several broadly disputed in the literature cases of application of the definitions of 'Deportation' and forcible 'Transfer' of population over the recent two decades; thus, highlighting a significant controversy and even few wrong-punishments in tackling the issue. Particularly in the case [IT-94-1-AR72] there is stated that the crimes under Article 8 (Rome Statute) are defined as very complex and not mutually coherently. Furthermore, there are considerable number of crimes that have never been uncovered within cases tackling war crimes^[34].

Importantly, as the commentary of the legal practice, so far, highlight that the essential understanding of the issue is that there is 'act(s)' when committed as part of a widespread or systematic attack directed against any civilian population. Therefore, the perpetrator committed the crime (*actus reus*) or it is individual committing or participating in the crime. Particularly, as great controversy has been regarded the application of *mens rea* standard (below).

Owing to the fact that the AWTs^[2] of **Subject 1-case** highlight children as civilian population the application of the common sense "*a widespread or systematic attack directed against*" indirectly falsifiable the strict application of the terms deportation and forcible transfer. Looking at the discussed cases so far, the case of transfer of children under Article 50 (protection of children) due to effect of war do not supposed to be treated as crime; furthermore, from the context of war crime under Article 8. An argument supporting for the latter statement is that the fact that international criminal responsibility included acts committed during internal armed conflict case [IT-94-1-AR72]; (<https://m.asylumlawdatabase.eu/sites/default/files/aldfiles/Prosecutor%20v%20Tadic%20%28IT-94-1-AR72%29%20ICTY.pdf>]; Decision on the Defence Motion for Interlocutory Appeal on Jurisdiction, 2 October 1995, (1997) International Law Reports, Vol. 105 ILR p. 453 [CL-0519; https://icsid.worldbank.org/sites/default/files/parties_publications/C8394/Claimants%27%20documents/CL%20-%20Exhibits/CL-0519.pdf], assumes that there is obligation to protect the children, due to the effect of the armed conflict, in spite of the fact that this conflict could not be explicitly classified as war. Not only are the specific acts set out in excruciating detail, the actual categories impose a difficult exercise of assessment of the type of armed conflict. Due to requirements to distinguish between international and non-international conflicts which could be complicated task by the fact that within the subset of non-international conflicts there are two distinct categories conflicts, there has been already shown how difficult this task of qualification can be as I have attempted to sketch in the preceding

subsection. It has been noted that there can be in principle covered even isolated crimes committed by individual soldiers acting without direction or guidance from higher up. Therefore, the War crime is attributed to isolated crimes by individuals in the most cases who are military mid-low level Rank servants. However, despite the complexity of the issue regarding classifications of type conflicts and definitions of crimes, in the discussed **Subject 1-case**, there is protection of the children under Article 50.

Further: The genocide and crimes against humanity would seem to be primary intervened by the ICTs. There should not always be the case for war crimes. The focus of intervening war crimes is on '*in particular when committed as a part of a plan or policy or as part of a large-scale commission of such crimes*'. Thus, the language brings war crimes closer to crimes against humanity. The Rome Conference found middle ground with the words 'in particular', thereby compromising between those favouring a rigid threshold and those opposed to any such limitation on jurisdiction^[35].

The Rules proscribing war crimes address the *conduct of a perpetrator* towards an immediate protected subject, while the Rules proscribing crimes against humanity address the perpetrator's conduct not only towards the immediate victim but also towards the whole of human kind. A particular attention is focused on the consequently affect due to crimes against humanity [IT-96-22-A/7.10.1997]; [<https://www.icty.org/x/cases/erdemovic/acjug/en/erd-aj971007e.pdf>]].

For the purposes of this contribution, I shall only stress that case [IT-96-22-A/7.10.1997][<https://www.icty.org/x/cases/erdemovic/acjug/en/erd-aj971007e.pdf>] among other examples distinguish between nationality of the victims and their ethnicity, as well.

As an attempt to address the latter issue, **Figure 1** sketches some inter-Institutional relationships, involving the Presidential Office and the **Subject 1** personally. Within the framework of the social-policy system of *public authority* the control power is by the Federal Assembly or State Duma. The public authority system is Constitutionally introduced *via* Article 67(1), Article 71(g), Article 80.2, Article 132.3 of the Constitution of the Russian Federation (2020) (consider the texts of the Constitutions of the Russian federation on 12.12.1993 and 01.07.2020). (Text of the RUSSIAN FEDERATION CONSTITUTION translated by the Constitutional Court for the Opinion (No. 992 / 2020) of the EUROPEAN COMMISSION FOR DEMOCRACY THROUGH LAW (VENICE COMMISSION) (Strasbourg, 4 February 2021) [CDL-REF(2021)010] [<https://www.coe.int/en/web/venice-commission/-/opinion-992>].)

Therefore, the so-called Executive Power Authorities^[36], *i.e.*, the Police, including Border Control Authority, Army, and Prison system, are under the control power by the Parliament. Furthermore, as shown in **Figure 1** the inter-Institutional relationships are strictly determined within the framework of both the Constitutional and the Federal Laws, which have supremacy within the Article 4(2) of the Russian Federation Constitution.

Despite, the fact that there is Constitutionally provided to the **Subject 1** Constitutional decree power within the framework of the Article 90 (1) of the Russian Constitution, the Presidential Decrees, despite the fact that also represent Laws, should not contradict neither the Constitution, nor the Federal Laws. Thus, the Presidential Decrees have lower legal status comparing with the Constitutional and the Federal Laws of the Russian Federation. Any Presidential decree can, in fact, be blocked by the Parliament.

Therefore, any social-policy "*plan or policy*" is by reference of *Public Authority* social-policy system of the Russian Federation. Within this System, **Subject 1** unable individually neither to commit war crime nor to apply any social-policy plan or policy in context of the discussed AWTs^[2]. The issue obviously calls for knowledge of social-policy system of the Russian Federation. The AWTs^[2] assume a rather lack of knowledge, which is rather doubtful and confusing in this case. We shall consider the issue below detailing on doctrines of ICR under Article 25^[1], Article 28^[2], and Article 30^[1]; thus, further highlighting why my statement is justified.

Herein, I should only note that inter-Institutional relations of the Russian Federation and legislature, within the System-Law of both the Constitutional and Federal Laws excludes from ICR **Subject 1** as individual committing crime as “*plan or policy*”, as well.

The Presidential Power of the Russia Federation is determined within the Article 104(1) of the Russian Constitution (2020) stating:

Article 104

(See Text of the RUSSIAN FEDERATION CONSTITUTION translated by the Constitutional Court for the Opinion (No. 992 / 2020) of the EUROPEAN COMMISSION FOR DEMOCRACY THROUGH LAW (VENICE COMMISSION) (Strasbourg, 4 February 2021) [CDL-REF(2021)010] [<https://www.coe.int/en/web/venice-commission/-/opinion-992>].)

1. The right of legislative initiative shall belong to the President of the Russian Federation, the Council of Federation, senators of the Russian Federation, deputies of the State Duma, the Government of the Russian Federation, and legislative (representative) bodies of constituent entities of the Russian Federation. The right of legislative initiative shall also belong to the Constitutional Court of the Russian Federation and the Supreme Court of the Russian Federation on issues within their competence.

The ‘*constituent entities*’ stated in Article 104(1) are determined within the framework of Article 5(1) of the same Constitution, stating:

Article 5

1. The Russian Federation shall consist of republics, krais, oblasts, cities of federal significance, an autonomous oblast and autonomous okrugs, which shall have equal rights as constituent entities of the Russian Federation.

As an attempt to further argue my statements, I would like to focus the reader attention on detailing on the Crime under Article 6^[1]:

“It is also the view of the Chamber that although a specific plan to destroy does not constitute an element of genocide, it would appear that it is not easy to carry out a genocide without such a plan, or organisation”. There is further note that “it is virtually impossible for the crime of genocide to be committed without some or indirect involvement on the part of the State given the magnitude of this crime.” They suggested that “it is unnecessary for an individual to have knowledge of all details of the genocidal plan or policy” [ICTR-91-1-T/21.05.1999;§ 94] [<https://www.refworld.org/jurisprudence/caselaw/ictr/1999/en/62079>]. Consider, also [ICTR-96-3-T], Judgment, 6 December 1999 [<https://www.refworld.org/jurisprudence/caselaw/ictr/1999/en/61942>].

We might try and further defend the statement that there is a lack of ICR of **Subject 1** as individual committing crime neither as individual conduct (act and omission) nor as “*plan or policy*”, with argument along the line of magnitude of victims. If the AWTs^[2] are assigned to hypothesized 20000 children^[18], then individual 20000 acts of deportation or transfer cannot be carried out physically by **Subject 1**. The latter fact, direct and indirect involves structural sub-units of the State, but Executive Power Authorities.

At this point, however, there could be added the principle of *nullum crimen (sine lege scripta, praevia, certa and stricta)* which is explicitly laid down *via* four forms *lex scripta, lex praevia, lex certa, and lex stricta*^[39]. From the context of the latter two forms, a person (individual, singular form) can only be punished for an act (*actus reus*) which has been defined with sufficient clarity and was not been extended by analogy. Particularly, when, there are [crimes], then, they are not resolved in favour of the suspect.

Further, a reader with some knowledge of the International Criminal and Domestic Law should notice that the term 'Crime' is in fact a term from the Domestic Criminal Code, which definition supplies the standards to be utilized for conceiving the term 'International crime' (p. 923^[14].)

The three characteristics of the crime should be highlighted for the purpose of this contribution:

- (a) (sic) that it is a harm, brought about by **human conduct**, which the sovereign power in the State desires to prevent;
- (b) that among the measures of prevention selected is the threat of punishment;
- (3) those legal proceedings of a special kind are employed to decide whether the person accused did in fact **cause the harm**, and is, according to law, to be held legally **punishable for doing so** (p. 924^[14]).

The highlights are on the words defining the act, which involves the accused in a general context into the crime as mainly committing crime individual. Therefore, the definition of crime has much in common with the *actus reus*, then the *mens rea* standard and is primary applied as conduct by an individual or a group individual which the Law actually treats as criminal. The legal consequences call such conduct a "crime."

In other words, the term 'Individual criminal responsibility' is primary addressed to perpetrator committing (actus reus) crime.

Similarly, the lack of ICR of **Subject 1** is obvious again due to argument along the line of the magnitude of the victims [children]. Looking at the latter definition the AWTs^[2] attributed 20000 cases of victims children^[18] to **Subject 1**. As I have written before, it is absurd!

Obviously, **Subject 1** is the wrong addressee of the AWTs^[2] even if there is hypothetically accepted that such crimes have been committed. Because of, as I have highlighted above, the protection of children from the effect of war under Article 50 of the Conventions cannot be regarded as crime, despite the fact that the classification of the armed conflict is complex.

Additional pro-argument regarding the statement that **Subject 1** is the wrong addressee of the AWTs^[2] can be provided *via* illustrating what there is understood practically under the term *individual criminal responsibility* in the context of Article 8^[1].

The ICR in committing war crime could be clearly illustrated with the "...*despoiling bodies of the deceased*" during military conflict or war crimes of "*sentencing or execution without due process*", due to the highlighted above definition encompassing conduct type crime of individual (perpetrator) committing the crime conduct.

Consider, also:

.... "*Torture and other inhumane acts were not perpetrated as part of a widespread or systematic attack against the civilian population. While they do not constitute crimes against humanity, they can be prosecuted as war crimes*"...(Syrian Arab Republic, A/HRC/22/59/05.02.2013, §103 [https://www.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/Documents/HRBodies/HRCouncil/RegularSession/Session22/A-HRC-22-59_sp.pdf].)

Consider, also:

..."*The incidents described show that armed groups opposed to the government have committed war crimes*".....(Syrian Arab Republic, A/HRC/22/59/05.02.2013, §57 [https://www.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/Documents/HRBodies/HRCouncil/RegularSession/Session22/A-HRC-22-59_sp.pdf].)

A particular attention needs the statements:

...."*On January 7, 2013, government forces regained control of XXX after indiscriminately shelling the town and clashing with the FSA for three days. They entered the town, searched house by house, and*

executed civilians or those hors de combat by shooting them at close range. Video footage of the deaths indicated that government forces executed women, children, and the elderly, thereby committing the war crime of murder..." (Syrian Arab Republic, A/HRC/22/59/05.02.2013, §50 [https://www.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/Documents/HRBodies/HRCouncil/RegularSession/Session22/A-HRC-22-59_sp.pdf].), and

...A large number of enforced disappearances perpetrated by government forces and allied militias were reported. No information was provided to families who inquired about the whereabouts of any of their members. The relatives of some detainees who approached officials were, in turn, detained, which justified others' fear of making similar inquiries...." (Syrian Arab Republic, A/HRC/22/59/05.02.2013, §80 [https://www.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/Documents/HRBodies/HRCouncil/RegularSession/Session22/A-HRC-22-59_sp.pdf].)

The latter statements have been provided not only to illustrate what there is understood legally under war crimes and what there is the legal meaning of ICR of the perpetrators as committing the acts themselves, but also to underline that the Judgment of the latter case have referred to war crime of this case of: *War crime of "collective punishment"*. It is not included in the Rome Statute, however.

Further: The classification individuals *victims* of '*grave breaches*' must be so-called '*protected persons*'. According to first three Geneva Conventions [<https://www.icrc.org/en/law-and-policy/geneva-conventions-and-their-commentaries>], this means members of armed forces of a party to the international armed conflict, while within the fourth Geneva Convention, the term '*protected persons*' is applied to individuals who must be 'in the hands of a Party to the conflict or Occupying Power of which they are not nationals'. Dealing with *nationality*, ICTs have stated that even *nationals* in the traditional international law sense, are protected if they cannot rely upon protection of the State of which they are citizens, due to that they belong to a national Minority [IT-94-1-A](Judgment, 15.07.1999; §§164–6) [<https://www.icty.org/x/cases/tadic/acjug/en/tad-aj990715e.pdf>]. According to ECs, the perpetrator needs not know nationality of the offender, it being sufficient that he, respectively, she knew that the victim belonged to an adverse party to the conflict. Due to scarce case law in the application of Geneva Conventions, many of the terms used to ICTY Statute (and the Geneva Conventions) still are regarded as awaiting judicial interpretation. Owing to the fact that, as has been aforementioned, the Rome Statute does not differ significantly as wording from the former Statutes the view by the ICTY should be addressed to the Rome Statute, as well.

Some Paragraphs of the listed Articles in the AWTs^[2] encompass multiple crimes. In such cases the explanatory note detail on ECs as following^[37]:

8(2)(a)(vii)-1 War crime of unlawful deportation and transfer.

8(2)(a)(vii)-2 War crime of unlawful confinement.

8(2)(b)(viii) The transfer, directly or indirectly, by the Occupying Power of parts of its own civilian population into the territory it occupies, or the deportation or transfer of all or parts of the population of the occupied territory within or outside this territory.

Toward, requirement of *unlawfulness* as established in the Rome Statute or in other parts of international law, particularly, IHL, is not usually set out in ECs.

Toward **Article 8(2)(a)(vii)**, there is also statement *that* both guilty intent and recklessness which may be likened to serious criminal negligence, due to the fact that there is a rather lack of specific case law on the mental element of this crime [IT-95-14-T, §§ 152; 122 ILR 1 at 64], [<https://www.icty.org/x/cases/blaskic/tjug/en/bla-tj000303e.pdf>]. The statement is the *accused intended to unlawfully confine the victim, and in so doing was aware of, or recklessly blind to, the factual*

circumstances that would render the confinement unlawful [IT-96-21-T, Annex 1, p. A1–8], [https://www.icty.org/x/cases/mucic/tjug/en/981116_judg_en.pdf].

Looking at the subordinate legislation, the ECs must be consistent with the Rome Statute.

The introduction of^[37] refers to Article 9 and definitions of ECs assisting in the legal interpretation and application of Article 8, among others; provisions regarding Article 21; some general principles used to the practice and applicable to the ECs; provisions regarding Article 30; structure of ECs; definitions of legal terms such as perpetrator under Articles 25 and 28, and more.

Article 8 (2) (a) (vii)-1

Elements

1. The **perpetrator** deported or transferred one or more persons to another State or to another location.
2. Such person or persons were protected under one or more of the **Geneva Conventions of 1949**.
3. The **perpetrator** was aware of the factual circumstances that established that protected status.
4. The conduct took place in the context of and was associated with an **international armed conflict**.
5. The **perpetrator** was aware of factual circumstances that established the existence of an armed conflict.

Article 8 (2) (a) (vii)-2

Elements

1. The **perpetrator** confined or continued to confine one or more persons to a certain location.
2. Such person or persons were protected under one or more of the **Geneva Conventions of 1949**.
3. The **perpetrator** was aware of the factual circumstances that established that protected status.
4. The conduct took place in the context of and was associated with an **international armed conflict**.
5. The **perpetrator** was aware of factual circumstances that established the existence of an armed conflict.

Article 8 (2) (b) (viii)

Elements

1. The **perpetrator**:

- (a) Transferred, directly or indirectly, parts of its own population into the territory it occupies; or (b) Deported or transferred all or parts of the population of the occupied territory within or outside this territory.
2. The conduct took place in the context of and was associated with an **international armed conflict**.
3. The **perpetrator** was aware of factual circumstances that established the existence of an armed conflict.

Looking at the text above one might be said that in all the cases there is referred to the so-called '**Perpetrator**'. Therefore, our understanding of the doing justice in this case should be linked with the corresponding **Perpetrator of crime(s)**; thus, requiring to apply reliable interpretation of the term '**Perpetrator**' of War Crime under the listed Articles above. Although we have taken reasoning regarding the term 'perpetrator' in the text of the Articles of the Rome Statute, herein, I only shall note that again the ECs reflect the individual perpetrator of the conduct.

At this point it should be underlined that no doubt that there should be readers who should be ready to concede that within the framework of my so-called interpretative-explanation of the Rome Statute there should be a vast variety of interpretations in each case both looking at the texts of the Rome Statute and ECs. As an attempt to respond adequately I would address such remark; if any, saying both the "Yes" and "No". Why?

The Elements clarify that while the prosecution process must establish these threshold elements of war crimes. There is needed not to prove that the perpetrator had knowledge of whether or not there was an armed conflict, or whether it was international or non-international. There is ICR for certain particularly severe violations of the treaties as *actus reus*.

Particularly, case [T-02-54-T/20.03.2009] states that both the crimes of deportation and forcible transfer of population have the same elements. There is difference only toward the destination [https://www.icty.org/x/cases/slobodan_milosevic/tdec/en/040616.pdf] (Case No. IT-02-54-T/20.03.2009); §79].

In addition, the practice so far shows that war crimes, on the other hand can in principle cover even isolated acts committed by individual soldiers acting without direction or guidance from higher up, as aforementioned, thus, broadly acknowledging that any troop can develop its own field dynamic and could become nearly unstoppable by internal forces; thus, reaching a '*relative autonomy*' (p. 19^[38]).

At this point it should be also emphasised on the so-called '*State responsibility*'. From the context of international crime, it refers to acts for which the state themselves is responsible (p. 927^[14].) The criticism that the use of 'State responsibility' in context crime has not completely legal sense. There is a problem of holding an entire population of a state responsible for the acts of their government authorities. Any sanction ultimately falls on all citizens of a State.

Due to these reasons the term 'International crime' is regarded as not entirely clear. However, from the perspective of the discussed case, the already developed theories provide us with a schemata for tackling such cases. There are three presuppositions: (i) *that there is a special class of rules protecting fundamental interests of the international community*; (ii) *that every state has a right to take steps to Insist on compliance with those rules*; and (iii) *that sanctions other than a request for reparation may be applicable when such rules are breached* (p. 931^[14].)

From the perspective of the current explanatory interpretative analysis of the AWT^[2]-wording and the pre-history of the Ukraine-Russia conflict as presented in **Figure 1**; I follow a philosophy of thinking stating that the request for explanation is in fact a request for information. In so doing, there becomes apparent immediately an obvious question regarding the request when there are already introduced Laws protecting the fundamental rights of the international community; for instance, the Human Rights Law, among others (under point (I)); and Ukraine already have applied a lot of steps in insisting compliance with those and many other available Rules and Laws (under (point (ii))), then why in the tackled, herein, case (**Subject 1-case**) involving "deportation of children and forcible transfer of children" there are not requested reparations seeking the 'State responsibility'? As aforementioned, the terms deportation is explicitly directly connected with conducts by individuals of the Executive Power Authorities, who are further controlled by the Federal Assembly.

According to Article 54(1)(a) of the Rome Statute^[1] there should have clarified the role of the State Party and their commitments to comply with the International Conventions on the Protection of Children's Rights; furthermore, it is duty, which is not reflected in the AWTs^[2]. Instead of, an ICR of the **Subject 1** for a large-scale and grave crime of deportation or transfer of 20000^[18] children has been attributed.

The latter paragraph comes in crude version due to the fact that legal term '*deportation*' request to define the term '*State Border*', as well. A deportation, can occur in fact when there is the so-called State Border. Focusing our attention on the latter term, however, a further interpretation is essential. What constitutes a State? The legal term '*State*' itself is connected with ownership of a given territory within the framework of the International Law^[40].

Owing to the State ownership Decree of USSR (below), the so-called Ukraine SSR (territory of the present-day Ukraine) is ownership of the Russian Federation as successor of USSR (Consider Article 67(1) of the Constitution of the Russian Federation.

Decree determining the socialization of the land (22.05.1922):

"The State is only possible owner of land".

Decree determined property in land in USSR dating 06.1922:

The private property in land is under certain limits, determined within Provision 1.

(1)...The right of property in buildings in towns and rural districts which are not municipalized by local soviets up to the date of publication of this decree...

(The right to transfer a lease does not cover plots of land in rural districts.)

(2) „Terms of agreement with local authorities managing land and the right of buildings thereupon in town or rural districts within a fixed period of the law, not to exceed forty-nine years“...

The R.S.F.S.R. Land Code of October 30, 1922, in Force Since December 1, 1922:

Article 1

The right of private ownership of land, subsoil, waters, and forests within the R.S.F.S.R. is forever abolished by the decisions of the All-Russian Congresses of the Soviets of Workers', Peasants', and Red Army Soldiers' Deputies based upon the clearly expressed will of the workers and peasants.

Article 67¹

(Constitution of the Russian Federation; Text of the RUSSIAN FEDERATION CONSTITUTION translated by the Constitutional Court for the Opinion (No. 992 / 2020) of the EUROPEAN COMMISSION FOR DEMOCRACY THROUGH LAW (VENICE COMMISSION) (Strasbourg, 4 February 2021) [CDL-REF(2021)010] [<https://www.coe.int/en/web/venice-commission/-/opinion-992>].)

1. The Russian Federation is the legal successor of the Union of SSR within its territory, and a legal successor (legal continuator) of the Union of SSR as regards membership in international organisations and their bodies, participation in international treaties, and as regards obligations of the Union of SSR foreseen by international treaties and its active assets outside the territory of the Russian Federation.

Looking at the history of the Ukraine-Russia relationships it is clear that any territorial claims by Ukraine are not only unjustified, but in fact illegal.

Regardless of the latter remark, the fact that the comments that I offer you are from ICTs on wording of the AWTs^[2], let me emphasize that the International Legal System is decentralized and fragmented. In it, the creation, application and execution of Laws is built on a structure and logic that differ from the Laws valid for each individual country. There is no centralized legislative system in international law. Laws are created by the subjects of international law themselves, and they can be of different views, many of which are unrelated and independent of each other. The Legal System, thus created is different from the more consistent Legal System of the internal legal order valid for each individual State. You yourself see identical texts of normative documents in Different Legal Systems. However, the general principle of Law seeks natural justice, and therefore the decisions of the ICTs follow this logic. Moreover, according to the decision of the Rome Conference that adopted the Convention (U.N. Doc. A/CONF.183/9 (1998) [<https://www.securitycouncilreport.org/un-documents/document/acconf1839.php>]), the term “motivation excluding criminal” responsibility is used instead of “defense” against the accusation.

Following the reasoning excluding ICR of **Subject 1**; and following the general logic of the Law-System and *doing Justice*, one wonders (a) that the Law dealing with Human Rights and Humanitarian Law are directly applicable to armed conflicts; (b) the seeking-truth and Justice does not ignore the role of the State Party in committing a crime during armed conflicts, as there are explicitly cases of finding responsibility on part of State, including the Russian Federation, and (c) the Russian Federation has also signed a series of agreements, including those dealing with children during armed conflict, such as, for example, Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Rights of the Child on the involvement of children in armed conflict (OptOroitCRC2000) and Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC1989); (d) the fact that in general Article 8(2)(b) concerns and applies to humanitarian and peacekeeping missions, as well as the fact that Article 8(2)(b)(viii) treats not only population of occupied country, but also its own population (*i.e.* it is irrelevant whether the children are Ukrainian or not) and is considered one of most controversial paragraphs of Article (8), why AWTs^[29] for a serious and widespread deportation of specific 20000^[18] children, giving a separate opportunity for re-categorization of the acts, attributed to a completely innocent and institutionally dissubordinate individual (**Subject 1**) with Institution dealin with Children's Rights in the Russian Federation, such as the President of the Russian Federation and the Presidency as an institution in general?

Neither the President personally nor the Presidency as Institution have any duties and rights in social activities towards children, as well as protection of their rights (**Figure 1**). As it becomes clear, there is a separate and institutionally independent Commission with delegated rights, duties, powers, and privileges relating to children's rights. Therefore, the President of the Russian Federation cannot be personally charged with war crimes as individual perpetrator, co-perpetrator or crimes «part of a plan or policy», *et cetera*.

In the context of the latter paragraph and the main purpose of the current contribution, I would like to emphasize the role of the State (the Russian Federation) in protecting the life, ensuring the existence, and development of children in a military conflict. This is a State Act according to the Humanitarian Law and what I would like to present are few texts of the above OptOroitCRC2000 and CRC1989 Conventions. Both the Conventions are signed by Ukraine and the Russian Federation.

Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Rights of the Child on the involvement of children in armed conflict of 25.05.2000 (OptOroitCRC2000); Signed by the Russian Federation on 24.09.2008; Signed by Ukraine on 28.08.1991.

Article 2

States Parties shall ensure that persons who have not reached the age of 18 are not forcibly recruited into their armed forces.

Article 6

1. Each State Party shall take all necessary legal, administrative and other measures to ensure the effective implementation of the provisions of the present Protocol within its jurisdiction.

3.....States Parties shall, where necessary, provide such persons with all appropriate assistance for their physical and psychological recovery and social reintegration.

Convention on the Rights of the Child of 20.11.1989, (CRC1989); Signed by the Russian Federation on 16.09.1990; Signed by Ukraine on 11.07.2005.

Article 6

1. States Parties recognize that every child has the inherent right to life.

2. States Parties shall ensure to the maximum extent possible the survival and development of the child.

I will not comment on how the “State Party” Ukraine complies with the laws included in these conventions that they themselves have signed (CRC1989 and OptOroitCRC2000), but we have seen as I said before children used as human shields, used as a protective military force, killed in the rubble, *etc.* Documented cases by the media and news.

Thus, other obvious problem of AWTs^[2] is that we cannot see Ukraine as State responsible for committed crime in their territory. Looking at evidences, facts, and arguments, so far, as well as a lack of open source evidences of **Subject 1-case** it does not seem to be truth that doing Justice *via* AWTs^[2] do so, in fact. The AWTs^[2] attribute ICR for crimes of deportation and (forsible) transfer to a High State Public Elected Official of the Russian Federation (**Subject 1**); thus, excluding for ICR of individuals-subordinate to and sub-structures of the Executive State Authorities of Ukraine, DNR-Oblast (17.05.2015–30.09.2022), and the Russian Federation. However, the term *deportation*, itself request State border. Neither the Presidential Office, nor **Subject 1** exercise command on control authority over Federal State Border Control Authorities of the Russian Federation.

Since, the term causal explanation is information about the causal (pre-)history of events or causal process which result in the events, a logic account for the latter issue should be that there is a lack of

neither deportation nor forcible transfer of children from the context of the legal definitions of these terms and their application to Justice, internationally.

Rather, if there are evidences, facts, and arguments regarding deportation of children across the State border of the Russian Federation, then there is probably namely case of protecting civilian population (children) from effect of war, as aforementioned. If it is, then more realistic should be to tackle the Ukraine-Russia conflicts since 24.02.2022 as *humanitarian intervention* as already highlighted. Perhaps, there should be radical opponents to my view. However, looking at controversies regarding legal definitions of crimes under Article 8^[1] and their closer relation with crimes under Article 7^[1] tackling some issues, there are various theories, explanations and applications as illustrated *via* several examples of cases of international armed conflicts over decades, which raised various sorts of standards applicable to concrete crime; furthermore, tackling subtle detail on conducted crimes. As has been illustrated, there are frequently a set of competitive definitions of a term some of which defined as still unclear, as well as looking at complexity of the Ukraine-Russia conflict, and dynamics of events it becomes apparently clear that even the developed, so far, theories and definitions are inapplicable to whole group of children (let us assume that AWTs^[2] involve the 20000^[18] cases of victims), due to reasons sketched, above. The developed theories, so far, define explicitly a set of Norms as an attempt to tackle exactly with a legal accuracy various type of crimes. Any explanation of a conduct by potential perpetrator or accused of committing crime should be casually explained, in this case with relation to various small groups of children or even individual cases; if any.

Why, I have written, if any? A particular remark on victimology of children in cases of deportation and transfer should be highlighted. The discussed crimes could be committed using coercive means. However, the cohesion does not mean explicitly violence. Despite, that there is deportation and forcible transfer, the so-called victims cannot be regarded as victims^[41].

If there is adopted a hypothetical view for any kind of 'State Policy', then Executive Power Authorities are independent within the Constitutional and the Federal Laws as well as the control is executed by the Federal Assembly (consider **Figure 1**).

Particularly, looking at hypothetical events until 24.02.2022, border control includes both the Ukrainian and Russian Border Control Authorities in addition to DNR-Oblast ones within the 17.05.2015–30.09.2022.

Therefore, the **Subject 1** as President of the Russian Federation cannot be involved into neither *actus reus* not *mens rea* standards to any kind of crimes under the jurisdiction of the Rome Statute; even, if any such conducts.

Looking at AWTs^[2], particularly important is to argue what there is understood under «*State control*» over Executive Power Authorities during military operations. The arguments are provided by decisions of ICTs, as well. The comments on are applicable to events; if any, dating since 24.02.2022.

Under «*State Control*» there is understood, control over subordinate armed forces or militias or paramilitary units. It may be of a general nature and must include more than provision of financial assistance or military equipment or training. This requirement does not, however, extend to issue of specific orders from State or its instructions for each operation carried out by them. Under international law, controlling authorities are not required to plan all operations of units dependent on them; to select their targets; or to give specific instructions regarding conduct of military operations and any alleged violations of IHL. The control required by international law may be considered to exist where a State (or, in the context of an armed conflict, a *Party in conflict*) has a role in organizing, coordinating or planning military actions of military group, in addition to financing, training and equipping or providing operational support to that group. Acts committed by group or its members may be considered to be acts of, *de facto*, State organs, regardless of any specific instructions from controlling State regarding

conduct of any of these acts ([IT-95-14/1-A, §§122] [<https://www.icty.org/en/case/aleksovski>]; [IT-96-21-A [<https://www.icty.org/x/cases/mucic/acjug/en/cel-aj010220.pdf>], §26]; [IT-95-14-T] [<https://www.icty.org/x/cases/blaskic/tjug/en/bla-tj000303e.pdf>], §75; 122 ILR 1 at 43).

Moreover, according to SOFA Agreement, signed in 28.05.1997 and in force of date 12.07.1999 [https://web.archive.org/web/20140321072522/http://www.mid.ru/bdomp/spd_md.nsf/0/BBC88CF0F9DF3F9F44257C9800383F4D], there is Article 15(1), stating:

Article 15

1. Transportation of troops, persons included in military formations, traveling individually and as part of military formations, weapons, military equipment and other material and technical resources, guards and specialists accompanying them, by all types of transport, which are carried out in the interests of the Black Sea Fleet of the Russian Federation, shall be carried out on a priority basis, observing border, customs and other types of state control when crossing the Russian-Ukrainian border in accordance with the current legislation of Ukraine.

Therefore, any transfer of people crossing State border of Ukraine and Russian Federation before 24.02.2022 is carried out under Ukrainian Border Control Authority, as well. If there is committed crime of deportation, then subjects belonging to Ukrainian Border Control Authority or Ukraine as State should be involved as co-perpetrator of crimes. Before 24.02.2022 there is a lack of international military operation of Russia within the territory of Ukraine. Perpetrators from Ukrainian Executive Authorities or State Ukraine are not reflected in the AWTs^[2]. The same is true for Donetsk People's Republic Oblast Executive Power Authorities including Border Control ones within the 17.05.2015–24.02.2022.

As an attempt to argue further my statement why **Subject 1** as President of the Russian Federation himself has not any kind of (individual) criminal responsibility regarding any case of (committed) crime connected with the Ukraine-Russia conflict; if any, I would like to underline explicitly few decisions by Tribunals of the United States of America, as well.

Explicitly, (individual) criminal responsibility have the commanders of both the attacking and defending troops. Consider detail on 289 F3d, 1283, 1288–1289 [<https://law.justia.com/cases/federal/appellate-courts/F3/289/1283/483592/>]; 782 F3d 576, 609 [<https://case-law.vlex.com/vid/doe-v-drummond-co-893905702>]; 384 F Supp. 3D 1328.

Explicitly, the role of the President during military operations is highlighted in the High Command Case (10/543 (1950); United States vs. Von Leep et al. [https://www.worldcourts.com/imt/eng/decisions/1948.10.28_United_States_v_Leeb.pdf]), showing the followings:

...“A commander holding a high hierarchical position cannot be fully informed of the details of a military operation of his subordinates and, without a doubt, of the administrative measures taken...”

In other words, the latter case rejects criminal responsibility of President for criminal acts of soldiers and administration.

1.4. The ‘Individual Criminal Responsibility’ under the Article 25^[1], Article 28^[1], and Article 30^[1]

The Article 25^[1], Article 28^[1], and Article 30^[1] treat the so-called ‘Individual Criminal Responsibility’. The provisions might be subdivided into objective elements (*actus reus*) and subjective ones (*mens rea*) detailing on issue of ICR. Particularly, Article 30^[1] deals with *mens rea* standards. The Rome Statute states^[1]:

Article 25⁸ (Individual criminal responsibility)

3. In accordance with this Statute, a person shall be criminally responsible and liable for punishment for a crime

within the jurisdiction of the Court if that person:

(a) Commits such a crime, whether as an individual, jointly with another or through another person, regardless of whether that other person is criminally responsible;

⁸As amended by resolution RC/Res.6 of 11 June 2010 (adding paragraph 3 *bis*).

The common understanding of the individual responsibility postulates personal sanctions^[42], as has been underlined still in the Abstract section of this contribution. Further, a single crime definition might request a different culpable state of mind (below) for the objective element of an offence; furthermore, *per* element. Essentially, this confuses further the idea to attribute in total 20000^[18] crimes to a single perpetrator, even not **Subject 1**. On the other hand, when there are claims of excuse; for instance, insanity or involuntary intoxication, then there is conceded that the conduct as act is wrongful, but the individual involved into the criminal act is not blameworthy or culpable. Since, this is basic understanding of the theory behind the Criminal Law^[43], I do not oppose it. Conversely, I attempt to focus on the fact that the application of the so-called "excuses" in doing Justice is on the individual actor or perpetrator of crime, and not the act itself. It is proven as crime. Thus, the do Justice considers does individual-accused is not blameworthy or culpable. The process involves assessment of whether there is any relevant excuse, however, for the accused's conduct, because of according to the crime equation there is Crime = "Fulfilment of actus reus and mental elements (*mens rea*)" + "Absence of Justification" + "Absence of Excuse". From the perspective of the major purpose of this contribution, the latter paragraph attempts to highlight that, herein, there is not discussed do 20000^[18] crimes really commit or not, but does **Subject 1** able to commit 20000 acts as individual actor or perpetrator of these hypothetical crimes. Both the application of the definitions of crimes under Article 6^[1], Article 7^[1], and Article 8^[1] and according to the foundations of the Theory of the Criminal Law as well as the case-examples of the ICTs practice tackling crimes of genocide, crimes against humanity, and war crimes, so far, have shown, that in the case of **Subject 1** it is an absurd.

This sub-section attempts to illustrate the inapplicability of Article 25 and Article 28 to **Subject 1**, as well.

The Objective Elements of ICR (*actus reus*) involve that an *individual* is criminal responsible for a crime under Article 6, Article 7, and Article 8 if he, respectively, she perpetrates; takes part in or attempts a crime within the Subparagraphs (a)–(f). Taken together Article 25(3) and Article 28 are regarded as a set of Rules of individual assignment to ICR and expanding individual assignment to specific form of participation in crime. However, the latter forms of involvement of the individual into liability may or may not still be determined as specific forms of involvement into crime.

There is a statement that the inclusion of the so-called "*collective liability*" would deflect from the Rome Statute's focus. It is chiefly on individuals. Furthermore, there is highlighted that there should be confrontation with serious and ultimately overwhelming problems of evidence in the case of seeking collective liability. Next, the highlights are on the not yet universally recognized common standards for the so-called "corporate liability". It is regarded as not even recognized in all major Criminal Law Systems^[44].

Despite, let us further concentrate on Rules of ICR. It is deduced that Subparagraph 25(3)(a) refers to perpetration, while Subparagraphs 25(3)(b) and 25(3)(c) refer to other forms of participation of the individual into crime. Since, the AWTs^[2] show Article 25(3)(a) and Article 28(b) assumes that due to the latter distinguishing of liability under Article 25(3), the involvement of Article 25(3)(a) into^[2] seeks of 'Perpetration'.

There are various forms of perpetration, however. The Subparagraph (a) distinguishes among direct or immediate perpetration "as an individual"; co-perpetration called "jointly with another"; and perpetration

by means called “through another person”. The co-perpetration is recognized as an autonomous form of perpetration.

The direct perpetration assumes committing crime as an individual; thus, stressing the individual’s own conduct committing by himself, respectively, acting by herself without relying on another person. Therefore, the crime is committed by the perpetrator alone or individually. Commissions of crimes “with” or “through” another person “regardless of whether that other person is criminally responsible” are tackled separately.

The major doubt regarding the sense of the latter sentence is due to the fact that the term ‘Perpetration’ presupposes that the individual who also commits crime could be used as a tool by indirect perpetrator. The term ‘Perpetration’ in such view, should be addressed to an innocent agent, who should not be responsible for the criminal act as a whole.

Commonly, under ‘Perpetrator’ by means is determined as principal or the individual committing the criminal act as discussed, above. As examples, when individuals could be used as tool or instrument acting and committing crime; for instance, erroneously or is not culpable are highlighted cases of minor age of the perpetrator-tool or his, respectively, her mental defect; if any. As far as, the individual using the perpetrator-tool for crime is regarded not criminally responsible this fact is recognized superfluous.

The co-perpetration liability shows various criminal tasks among co-perpetrators, who should be interconnected by a common plan or agreement for committing crime. A particular remark is on the view that every co-perpetrator fulfils a set of tasks; thus, contributing to the crime commission; and, explicitly without these tasks the crime commission would not be possible. The so-called common plan or agreement holds every co-perpetrator liable for the whole crime.

Although, that the wording of AWTs^[2] involves only Article 25(3)(a), I shall emphasise on the other form of participation, as well as, because of interpretation of Subparagraphs (b) and (c) also involves superior-subordinate relations within the various degree of responsibility. Subparagraph (b) deals with individual who orders, induces or solicits crime commission or attempt of a crime, while Subparagraph (c) detail on any other assistance of committing crime such as “aids, abets, *et cetera*, including providing the means in the crime commission or attempt of committing crime in cases of facilitating it.

The individual who orders a crime is regarded as perpetrator by means rather than accomplice, using a subordinate to commit the crime. The identical Article 2(1)(b) in the 1996 Draft Code of Crimes has been regarded as intended to implement provide liability of mainly mid-level officials who order their subordinates to commit crimes^[45].

An alternative in Subparagraph (b) regarding (“[o]rders”) complements the provision of the *Doctrine of Command Responsibility* under Article 28. The superior is liable for an act “*omission*”, in fact, in the case of an (existing) order to commit a crime [to the subordinate] the superior is liable for commission. The omission in this case is regarded as a lack of order preventing the commission of the crime by the subordinate. A statement called that this alternative in Subparagraph (b) overlaps some forms of perpetration under Subparagraph (a) being a form of crime commission “*through another individual*.” Under “*Soliciting a crime*” there is understood *inter alia*, to request, command, encourage, or incite another individual to engage him, respectively, her, in specific conduct to commit crime. In other words, there is reflected in mind an individual influencing another individual to commit a crime. The word “inducing” is regarded to encompass any conduct or encourage causing another individual for committing crime, including to soliciting that individual.

Further, it should be said that the link between the act contributing to the commission of crime and the act of crime itself (crime scene) can be geographically and temporally different.

The latter statement provides further pro-argument regarding my correct spatial-temporal treatment of the hypothetically committed crimes according to AWTs^[2]; thus, requesting a well-determined groups of victim children *per* the shown in **Figure 3** spans of time and encompassing both the territory of

Ukraine and the DNR Oblast within 17.05.2015–30.09.2022. The well-determined various phases of the Ukraine-Russia conflict seems to not be a continuum among so significant number of cases (20000^[18] (!)). The latter statement assumes that, despite the fact that AWTs^[2] state regarding children in plural form, first, this does not mean that there are the referred in the news showing at about 20000 cases^[18]. The AWTs^[2] do not claim to actually observe the victim cases within short span of time or spatial location. Thus, the lack of concreteness and clarity regarding neither the total number of potential victims, nor spatial distribution of the cases of their temporal one, in fact, further undermine the objectivity of interpreting and applying such large number, overlapped and even controversial definitions of perpetration and co-perpetration even looking only at Article 25(3).

Furthermore, the Rome Statute does not provide solution for complicity acts, but after a crime commission. Such acts; if any, are tackled within the concept of complicity if they were connected with commonly plan and agreement of crime commission. Otherwise, the individual would be liable pursuant to a distinct offense [[IT-94-1], §692] extended liability in the latter context to “*all that naturally results from the commission of the act in question*”.

From the major purpose of this study, however, the interpretation and application of Article 25(3)(a), I shall illustrate first looking at case [ICC-01/04-01/06-8-US corr 10.02.2006], [<https://www.icc-cpi.int/court-record/icc-01/04-01/06-8-corr>] stating that strictly commission of crime is understood as crime by person as individual joined with another or through another. Therefore, there are requested minimum two individuals perpetrators of crimes in the context of *actus reus*. Second, there should be agreement in common plane of committing crimes. In addition, Article 25(3)(a) is used to mid-low militaries killing-group people.

Conversely, case [ICC-01/04-02/12-4, Trial Chamber II/18.12.2012], [<https://www.icc-cpi.int/court-record/icc-01/04-02/12-4>] states that within the context of the so-called *joint perpetration* under Article 25(3)(a)^[1] there is not requested direct contribution; thus, impacting the manner in which the material element of the crime is realise. This does not mean direct presence on the crime scene. The view includes indirect co-perpetration of crime *via* planning and coordination. The major criticism of this view is that it expands Article 25(3)(a)^[1] to inconsistency with Article 22(2)^[1] of the Rome Statute.

Article 22^[1] (Nullum crimen sine lege)

2. The definition of a crime shall be strictly construed and shall not be extended by analogy. In case of ambiguity, the definition shall be interpreted in favour of the person being investigated, prosecuted or convicted.

If there is applied consequently the already discussed legal matter and interpretations of terms to AWTs^[2], then the points we have, so far, in this sub-section should be compatible with ‘War Crimes’ under Article 8^[1], which are as aforementioned classified as conduct type crimes. In the latter context, the Criminal Law has strong communicative function to adhere the principle of legality. The conduct (act) must be accurately characterized as act or (I highlight the word or) an omission of duty. It is the so-called Duff’s control test^[46].

If it is the so, then there is the following argument, the arrest warrant texts including **Articles 8(2)(a)(vii)** and **8(2)(b)(viii)** and **Article 25(3)(a)** rather surmise that **Subject 1** has committed or has ordered commission of crimes within a direct subordinative relation superior-subordinate as perpetrator (*actus reus*); furthermore, within mid-low (military) group people or, perhaps, troops. Despite the forms of perpetration sketched above, *i.e.*, “as an individual”, “jointly with another”, and “through another person”, the application of Article 25(3)(a), however, mostly refers as to duties of military commanders toward “to control”/“order” of their troops.

Particularly, the attempt is to define the commanders know of widespread crimes committed in territory under their direct command, respectively, control. Owing to that individual can only be punished under the *Rome Statute* for an act codified at time of its commission (*lex scripta*), was defined with sufficient clarity (*lex certa*) and was not extended by analogy (*lex stricta*), among other, there is key problem (6).

Key problem (6): The hypothetical crimes addressed to **Subject 1** as perpetrator (*actus reus*) are not clarified and perhaps extended by analogy looking to the major direction of the shown **Articles 8(2)(a)(vii)** and **8(2)(b)(viii)** and **Article 25(3)(a)** applicable mainly to war crimes committed within the framework of direct subordinative relation superior-subordinate of mainly military commanders and the relations within the framework of military servants of a troop and their commander (or there are small group actors) in tackling mainly crimes committed within the territory under direct command or control by the commander.

If the AWTs^[2] refer to the Rank of the **Subject 1** in tackling the hypothetical crimes in Ukraine, then as **Figure 1** shows the military service by **Subject 1** ended 01.09.2000. His Rank is kept, but not his service to the Institutions of the Executive Power Authorities, due to Decree 1602/01.09.2000 and (Article 17(2), FL: 349-Φ3).

The Institutions Presidency, Army, Police, Prison system, and more, operate independently (Decree 1602/01.09.2000-present; and FL: 349-Φ3/08.12.2020-present) within the written (there is a lack of oral) Federal Laws and their inter-Institutional Codes, which do not contradict the Constitution and the Federal Laws (Article 17(3), FL: 349-Φ3).

Therefore, since 01.09.2000, **Subject 1** does not has any kind of subordinative relationships with structures, sub-structures, and individuals as staff members of the Executive Power Authority of the Russian Federation.

In addition, the Office of the Presidency lack of exercising control over the Executive Power Authorities.

The Rules (Law 457/07.08.2017) applied to the State-Border Control used to FSB are strictly determined with the Law 4730-I/01.04.1993 (consider Article 4). The governing and control authority of the Heads of Department of the FSB sub-structures including *per* Oblast are determined within the framework of Federal Law 40-FL/03.04.1995 (updated 18.06.2017) (Consider Article 1 and Article 2).

Article 2 40-FL/03.04.1995 (updated 18.06.2017):

.... *The management of the regions is provided by the territorial security bodies [by regions]...The territorial security bodies are subordinate to the Federal Security Service (FSB).*

Therefore, Article 25(3)(a) is inapplicable to **Subject 1** as accused of committing of war crimes under Article 8; if any.

In other words, a doctrine (Command Responsibility) which is designed and chiefly applied to mid-low militaries group people (mostly troops) who are mutually directly subordinative linked is obviously inapplicable to **Subject 1** as individual High State Public Elected Official; furthermore, accounting for that the Presidential Institution is independent from Executive Power Authorities; and, in addition to lack of both the command and (effective) control authority functions.

The latter arguments could be made more powerful looking at Article 28^[1]. It states:

Article 28^[1] (Responsibility of commanders and other superiors)

In addition to other grounds of criminal responsibility under this Statute for crimes within the jurisdiction of the Court:

(b) With respect to superior and subordinate relationships not described in paragraph (a), a superior shall be criminally responsible for crimes within the jurisdiction of the Court committed by subordinates under his or her effective authority and control, as a result of his or her failure to exercise control properly over such subordinates,

where:

- (i) The superior either knew, or consciously disregarded information which clearly indicated, that the subordinates were committing or about to commit such crimes;
- (ii) The crimes concerned activities that were within the effective responsibility and control of the superior; and
- (iii) The superior failed to take all necessary and reasonable measures within his or her power to prevent or repress their commission or to submit the matter to the competent authorities for investigation and prosecution.

The Article 28^[1] Subparagraph (b) details on ICR of civilian superiors. The text of the Article 28 (b) explicitly highlights words as 'superior', 'subordinative relations', and 'control over' subordinates.

The Article 28^[1] is broadly discussed in the specialized literature as presenting a large number of problems, particularly toward control of civilian superior over his, respectively, her subordinates. Particularly, the civilian superiors are frequently not in the position to prosecute acts committed by their subordinates. The latter fact can be true for military commanders, as well. In such cases; if any, there should be submission the matter to corresponding Executive Power Authorities, explicitly referring to the Police and Prosecutors; also, to the Court.

The Article 28^[1] (a) addresses mainly military commander or person effectively acting as a (military) commander, who shall be criminally responsible from crimes committed by forces under his, respectively, her effective command or control or effective authority or control as well as cases when he, respectively, she fails to exercise control property over such (sub)-structures under his, respectively, her direct control and command^[47].

The superior-subordinates command relationships are underlined as *factual test*. The commander may be held liability for act of subordinates only if the subordinates are under his, respectively, her formal command (Article 87 (Duty of commanders) [<https://ihl-databases.icrc.org/en/ihl-treaties/api-1977/article-87/commentary/1987>])).

However, ICTs do not attribute strict liability to military commanders whenever their subordinates committed war crimes. Precisely, what there is requested from commanders is apparent still from less certain laws; furthermore, having various formulations.

Due to these reasons, I should not further detail on doctrines of direct and indirect command responsibility not only because of they are chiefly applied to cases of mid-law military commanders. The application of the doctrine of indirect command responsibility applied to case [IT-03-68/Judgment/30.0606/§294], [<https://www.icty.org/en/case/oric>] has been broadly debated, due to significant controversy of formulation of its three-step approach.

An objective analysis should extend the discussion to account for numerous ICTs cases, including involvement of wrong liability modes using not valid law and processing war crimes of mid-low level military commander-subordinate relations. Despite, there are cases of wrong-punishments, including against High Level Public Officials, as well. The latter scope is outside the goal of the current analysis. As I have written above, it does not reject neither the Norms, nor the concepts behind them. It attempts to stress that these Norms and doctrines are wrongly addressed to **Subject 1** as a hypothetically accused perpetrator of war crimes within the wording of AWTs^[2].

The command responsibility doctrine, cannot be presumed by "*de jure command*"; thus, distinguishing between "*de facto*" and "*de jure*" command. In case [IT-96-21-A/20.02.2001/§193,§197], [<https://www.icty.org/x/cases/mucic/acjug/en/cel-aj010220.pdf>] under "*de facto command*" there is understood the actual ability to control the subordinates behaviour at the time of the crime conducts. This view assumes that **Subject 1** as *de facto* (not *de jure*) commander presents in crime scene, during the conduct. As I have written before, such argument says that **Subject 1** is accused as actual perpetrator as individual, but indirectly. Again, he should have in this case presumably committing 2000^[18] crimes or 2000 conducts. Absurd!

Briefly, I shall focus the reader attention on the so-called "*effective control*" through examining four objective factors. The major points have been detailed in case [ICC-01/05-01/0833434/21.03.2016/§180], [<https://www.icc-cpi.int/car/bemba>] together with views in case [ICTR-

96-13-T/27.01.2000, §800], [<https://www.refworld.org/jurisprudence/caselaw/ictr/2000/en/64129>] determining “*de facto control*” and “*de jure control*”.

In the latter case the ability to terminate employment has been considered as criminal.

As four objective factors determining the “effective control” there is understood [ICC-01/05-01/0833434/21.03.2016/§180], [<https://www.icc-cpi.int/car/bemba>]:

- (i) capacity of issue order;
- (ii) whether the orders are in fact followed;
- (iii) authority issues disciplinary measures; and
- (iv) power to terminate the employment of subordinates, respectively.

As an attempt to argue for inapplicability of these objective factors and views both regarding the so-called “*effective control*” and “*de facto control*” from the context of the preceding paragraph to the case of **Subject 1**, my interpretation shall refer again to **Figure 1**. It attempts to illustrate the major inter-Institutional relations between the Presidential Office of the Russian Federation, the Executive Power Authorities, and the Commission for Children’s Rights, among few other Authorities/Institutions.

Despite the fact that the Commission for Children’s Rights is at the Presidential Office, they operate independently within the framework of Federal Law 349-FZ/08.12.2020-present, Decree 986/01.09.2009-present, and FL: 501-FZ/27.12.2018-present. Second, the Presidential Office, and particularly, the President of the Russian Federation have not exercised control over the Commission for Children’s Rights.

The Commission is not subordinate to Presidency, but to a report, annually, therein. Regarding, information provided, within the inter-Institutional relation between Commission for Children’s Rights and the Presidential Office, I should add, herein, what there is understood under Article 28(2) applied to information provided.

“Civilian superiors can similarly be held responsible for crimes committed by subordinate by their effective control and authority if they knew or continuously disregarded information which clearly indicate that the subordinate was committing or about to commit crime”.

As can be seen, again, there should be superior-subordinate relations. However, there is a lack of subordinative relation **Subject 1-Subject 2** of type superior-subordinate, due to reasons sketched above. The latter example of case also illustrates inapplicability of Article 28(2) to **Subject 1-Subject 2** type superior-subordinate network, due to lack of such as relationship.

Further: “Act for the Protection of Victims of Torture” [<https://www.internationalrightsadvocates.org/about-torture-victims-prevention-act-tvpa>] lists as ECs existence of superiority-subordinate direct perpetrator of a crime doctrine (or Article 28 (b)^[1]).

The Article 30^[1] is not explicitly shown in AWTs^[2]. It requires that *mens rea* standard of the material elements of a crime involve commitment with intent and knowledge. Its strict application, so far, shows exceptions, particularly in cases of Article 28^{[1][48]}.

In detailing on application of Article 25(3)(a) to a relation **Subject 1-Subject 2**, I should mention the JEC doctrine, which is designed to impose ICR on an individual (accused) for participation in a group’s common criminal plan^[49,50]. Briefly, the doctrine treats co-perpetration without act. First, the JEC theory of liability has been applied to case [IT-94-1] [<https://www.icty.org/x/cases/tadic/acjug/en/tad-aj990715e.pdf>], however, it is object of enormous debates and criticism, mainly connected with *mens rea* element (iii) ‘*participation of accused in common design*’. There is stated that its application leads to violation of principle of culpability. The concept of culpability, commonly presuppose an individual participation in crime, but as act. There is needed to commit and observe a wrongful act in order to apply criminal liability. The plan of crime does not refer to criminal act, without committed individually crime. Since, the issue is broadly addressed in the literature, it needs particular attention which shall be provided in a separate contribution, mostly

due to that as all doctrines discussed so far and connected with AWTs^[2] tackle superior-subordinate command or (effective) control relations.

For the purpose of this contribution, I shall only provide example how is applied JEC doctrine to ICTs-practice. It is already used to case when military commander orders soldiers under his command to kill individuals, belonging to a well-defined group people, using the racial criterion. The soldiers of his troop have killed a number of individuals-victims. Since, the group individuals are well-determined as ethnic one, there is proven that the soldiers have *genocidal intent* at the time of the act of killing, and the military commander is aware of that intent. The soldiers are determined as principal perpetrators of crimes; furthermore, they have satisfied elements of genocide by killing. There is in force of Article 6(a)^[1]. They are found guilty of committing genocide under Article 25(3)(a)^[1]. The military commander who ordered them to kill the ethnic group individuals appears accessory and is found guilty of ordering genocide under Article 25(3)(b)^[1].

I strongly hope that this example of real case persuasively illustrates how is applied Article 25(3)(a) and how inapplicable is it toward **Subject 1-Subject 2** relation.

However, I should refer to Article 54(1)^[1] stating that AWT(s)^[2] should agree with '(a) *In order to establish the truth, to expand the investigation so as to cover all facts and evidence relevant to the assessment of whether there is criminal liability under this Statute, and thus to investigate equally incriminating and exculpatory circumstances.*

The current AWTs^[2] seem to contradict the Article 54(1)(a)^[1] assessing ICR the individuals.

The control over the Commission for Children's Rights is exercised by the Federal Assembly. Within the framework of the social-policy legal system of *Public Authority* both the Upper Chamber and the State Duma can induce, among a set of initiatives, a Prosecution investigation into an allegation of a crime^[51]. In addition, there are a set of available Legislative Committees, particularly, highlighting the State Duma; for instance, (i) *Defense*; (ii) *Security*; (iii) *Affairs of Women, Family, and Children*; and more^[52], who tackled the issue regarding Executive Power Authorities and the Commission for Children's Rights.

From the context of "dismissing" the Commissar, the **Subject 1** as President lacks of authority to issue (disciplinary) dismissal of the Commissar; for instance. The term dismiss assumes that subordinate *is incapable of doing his, respectively, her job to the required standard*. The assessment of the determined, standards, however, request competence. The competence of **Subject 1** does not fit off the competences required for the Commissar employment position at the Commission for Children's Rights. Disciplinary dismissal is *when the employer decides to terminate a contract due to a serious breach of contract* by the employee. The latter is applicable only to direct superior-subordinate relations. Due to lack of direct superior-subordinate relations, he also lacks of power to terminate employment of employees at the Commission for Children's Rights, as well.

Therefore, any complaints against the Commissar and/or Commission for Children's Rights; if any, should be described/induced by the Federal Assembly, State Duma or Ombudsman, depending on the complaint type and addressed in front of the Court, due to Article 47 (1) of the Constitution of the Russian Federation stating that any citizen's case should be heard by judge within the corresponding competence.

Article 47 (1)

(Constitution of the Russian Federation; Text of the RUSSIAN FEDERATION CONSTITUTION translated by the Constitutional Court for the Opinion (No. 992 / 2020) of the EUROPEAN COMMISSION FOR DEMOCRACY THROUGH LAW (VENICE COMMISSION) (Strasbourg, 4 February 2021) [CDL-REF(2021)010] [<https://www.coe.int/en/web/venice-commission/-/opinion-992>].)

Nobody may be deprived of the right to have his (her) case heard in the court and by the judge within whose competence the case is placed by law.

Similarly, we might further detail on superior-subordinate relations of **Subject 1** and staff members of Executive Power Authorities, despite their internal-formal Military or Police Officers hierarchy. As **Figure 1** sketches within the framework of at least Decree 1602/01.09.2000-present; 349-FZ/08.12.2020-present; and 185-FZ/01.07.2011 to 391-FZ/05.12.2017-present; the Presidential Office and the Institutions the Police, the FSB, the Army, and more, are completely mutually independent. Their inter-Institutional subordinative structures and hierarchy are according to written Rules and Laws which do not contradict to the Constitution of the Russian Federation and the Federal Laws.

Therefore, there is a lack of superior-subordinate direct or indirect relations involving **Subject 1** with the staff of the Executive Power Authorities despite their positions occupied within the framework of the corresponding inter-Institutional hierarchy.

Particularly, looking at FSB, there could be further highlighted the Rules (Law 457/07.08.2017) applied to State-Border Control. They are strictly determined within the Law 4730-I/01.04.1993. The governing and control authority of the Heads of Department of the FSB sub-structures including *per* Oblast; for instance, are determined within the Federal Law 40-FL/03.04.1995 (updated 18.06.2017) (Consider Article 1 and Article 2).

Thus, **Subject 1** lacks of power to terminate the employment of staff members of the discussed Institutions due to lack of superior-subordinate relations. Toward, objective factor (iii) mentioned above, again **Subject 1** unable to/lacks of (iii) authority to issue disciplinary measures or disciplinary dismiss. Despite, the fact that Federal Law of FSB 40-FZ/03.04.1995 (updated 18.06.2017) states:

Article 1

(Federal Law of FSB 40-FZ/03.04.1995 (updated 18.06.2017)/Russian Federation)

"Heads of Federal Executive Bodies are appointed and dismissed from office by the President"

There is only approval of already induced by FSB candidature by the President; and '*dismiss*' in the context of released from debt due to retirement, resignation due to mutual agreement, and more, but, excluding disciplinary dismissal. There is valid the Constitutional Law Article 47 (1) obligating competence by authority. The **Subject 1** lacks of competence within the Article 47 (1).

The most debatable issue of the Article 28^[1] is the different mental requirement (*mens rea*) for civilian superiors comparing with military commanders. The Command Responsibility doctrine states that military commander is individually criminally responsible for crimes committed by his, respectively, her subordinate for which he, respectively, she "*should have known*". This is different subjective standard comparing with this for civilian superiors. There is a statement that the Rome Statute makes difficult to prosecute and exercise control properly within the relation superior-subordinate(s) in the case of civilian superior; thus, ignoring the traditional command responsibility doctrine [No. IT-94-2-R 61] (Review of Indictment Pursuant to Rule 61, Oct. 20, 1995, §24) [https://www.icty.org/x/cases/dragan_nikolic/tord/en/951020.pdf]; [IT-95-5-R 61/IT-95-18-R 61] (Review of Indictment Pursuant to Rule 61, July 11, 1996, §§42, 65–85) [<https://digitallibrary.un.org/record/237042>]; [No. IT-96-21-T] (Judgement 16 November 1998, §333)[<https://www.icty.org/en/case/mucic>].

Particularly, case ([ICTR-96-4-A], §§ 487–491; [<https://www.internationalcrimesdatabase.org/Case/50/Akayesu/>]) states that command responsibility of civilians "remains contentious" (§ 491).

Since, the issue of this analysis deals with superior-subordinate relationships within the framework of civilian officials I should discuss that in this case a civilian superior is individually criminally responsible only if he, respectively, she "*consciously disregarded information which clearly indicated*" that the subordinates were committing or they are about to commit a crime^[53].

Further: The restriction of the Rome Statute toward command responsibility doctrine in cases of civilians is regarded as a result of dogmatic inconsistencies of the doctrine itself. As major drawback is accepted the doubtful issue whether negligence, which is still sufficient for cases of military commanders could be logically construed toward commission of (special) intent crimes. At this point I should mention that the implication of Article 28^[1] into the arrest warrant texts causes for serious problem for the reliable and adequate interpretation and explanation of the wording of the texts mainly, due to a large number elusive and not strictly determined terms allowing re-categorization of crimes or adding of crimes during Trial, which have been broadly criticised, as well. Due to this reason, I shall only briefly extend herein the standards for *mens rea* for crimes under Article 7^[1] requesting in cases when a military commander negligently commit a crime together with the general *mens rea* standard under Article 30^[1] also a specific knowledge regarding the act's commission "*as part of a widespread or systematic attack*". The remark, herein is, perhaps the most serious one for the tackling the issue because of the commander's knowledge of a committed crime by subordinate assumes that the subordinate should report to the commander his, respectively, her commission of crime. The latter remark is particularly highlighted tackling the crimes under Article 6^[1], where further is requested not only knowledge, but also intent to destroy physically a well-determined and different by others group people if the perpetrator does not even know that his, respectively, her subordinate are in fact committing the crime. It is highlighted, particularly, that "it is impossible to commit a crime of intent by negligence."^[54,55]. From the context of the current AWTs^[2] there should be added that there is novel standard for civilian superiors attempting to show how the intent could be logical impasse. Despite, attempts in tackling legally superior-subordinate relations in cases of civilian superiors, there should be stressed that as **Figure 1** clearly shows the Presidential Institution and the Commission of the Children's Rights are not subordinative mutually connected. Thus, **Subject 1** and **Subject 2** are not in subordinative relations.

Furthermore, even looking the fact that the Command Responsibility doctrine also establishes liability for *omission*, where the superior is punished due to his, respectively, her lack of control of the subordinates as well as a failure to prevent or repress the commission of crimes, then, the superior is only responsible in case of effective authority and control. The obvious point, herein, is that Article 28^[1] is applied to relations superior-subordinate when there are cases of exercising direct command, effective authority and control. Therefore, in the discussed **Subject 1-case**, involving civilian superior **Subject 1** in crimes under Article 28(2)(b)^[1] could be carried out only when the civilian superior failed to take all necessary and reasonable measures, when there are effective authority and control by the civilian superior over the subordinate(s). The latter development of the theory of the command responsibility is an attempt of tackling mainly subordinative relations when the superior is civil while the subordinates could be military servants. In such cases, if any, then, the civilian superior is conceptually liable for a crime of an omission, for doing nothing to prevent the committing of the committed by his, respectively, her troops. It is also applicable, in cases when there is a lack of complete control over troops in the field if it was possible to retain control (pp. 48–50^[55])[U.N. Doc. A/CONF.183/C.1/WGGP/L.4/Add.1 (1998)]

[https://digitallibrary.un.org/record/259946/files/A_CONF.183_C.1_WGGP_L.4_Add.1_Rev.1-EN.pdf]. The latter paragraph and the relevant references, therein, I hope that persuasively illustrates to which cases and subordinative relations there is applied Article 28^[1]. As **Figure 1** shows, the superior-subordinate relations between **Subject 1** and **Subject 2** are completely different as kind of entities, thus, making Article 28^[1] inapplicable to **Subject 1** as accused of committing any type of the discussed crimes as civilian superior even having Rank.

In cases, when there is legitimacy of command responsibility which can hardly be questioned – in the case of positive knowledge of the superior – the delimitation between liability (command responsibility)

for omission (superior responsibility) and acting as an accomplice (complicity) is vague. There is the so-called culpable omission causing for *actus reus* criminal liability which covers the doctrine Aiding and Abetting by Omission. The case [IT-05-88-T/10.06.2010] [<https://www.icty.org/x/cases/popovic/tjug/en/100610judgement.pdf>] highlights, that the omission must constitute substantial assistance to underlined crime.

However, an omission that equates to substantial assistance might still not be commensurable with failure to fill a duty. The duty must be '*duty of guarantee*' in order to found criminal responsibility for the latter doctrine (*i.e.*, Aiding of abetting by omission [IT-95-13/1], [<https://casebook.icrc.org/case-study/icty-prosecutor-v-mrksic-and-sljivancanin>]). The particular remark in the latter context is the real application the Law to the facts, where in the cases of [IT-05-88-T/10.06.2010, §1551][<https://www.icty.org/x/cases/popovic/tjug/en/100610judgement.pdf>], the duty of the accused has been to protect prisoners and assure that they will not be harmed.

The next example of the latter context, *i.e.*, application of the doctrine aiding and abetting by omission tackles case [IT-05-88-T/10.06.2010, §1019], [<https://www.icty.org/x/cases/popovic/tjug/en/100610judgement.pdf>] and highlights the lack of conception of the duty of guarantee, showing that there could be imposing responsibility even in cases when there is even breach of duty. It is further argued that only true form of omission of aiding and abetting is superior responsibility doctrine^[56]. However, how can be defined the true form of omission when there is stated imperative need of border of liability mode; thus, requesting exact definition of the terms?

Some problems of implying liability within the framework of the doctrines of Command Responsibility or Superior responsibility have been detailed on [Darcy, 20 LJIL 2007, 377, at 390-392.]

Case [IT-97-25-A/17.09.2003, §102], [<https://www.icty.org/x/cases/krnjelac/acjug/en/krn-aj030917e.pdf>] approaches the duty issue from accused's position as responsible for welfare as detains warden acting his ultimate. It is regarded as closest example supporting the statement that it is never established act-omission equivalence. Because of, there is a statement that fallacious equivalences of omission to action. Therefore, omission is different from action or commission of crime. The distinction between omission and act is further tackled in [ICTR-01-65-T/11.09.2006, §22], [<https://www.legal-tools.org/en/doc/ce61de/>].

The most important in distinguishing between act and omission is to tackle counter facts and the causality. The direct causality refers to knowledge which depends on antecedent facts. Therefore, in order a superior to know this means that he, respectively, she should be recognized with the fact regarding the committed crimes. Due to these reasons, there is also debates in the criminal law field as to whether omission in fact causes for anything. The omission is literally nothing at all. Commonly, the cognitive knowledge refers to observation and experience. Knowledge of facts, therefore; if any, should mean observing and experiencing the facts. In the context of this contribution, the knowledge to results of crime. For instance; death, or injury. Thus, one should be practically certain that one's conduct should bring about crime results. It is connected with the mental-state terminology within the *mens rea* standard in addition to purpose, recklessness, and negligence (consider detail on^[43]).

Apart from the structural similarities between the discussed forms of derivative liability, evidence in war crimes Trials permits conclusions in both directions. A superior who has knowledge of atrocities of his, respectively, her troops can be held responsible as an accomplice (aiding and abetting) by, at least psychologically, encouraging and supporting the troops; or the superior can be held responsible by means of command responsibility for failure to prevent the atrocities. *Via* Rule 6185 the ICTY decisions have used both forms of liability. For example, case [IT-95-5-I] [<https://www.icty.org/x/cases/mladic/ind/en/kar-ii950724e.pdf>] was deemed responsible for the planning of genocide and for failure to prevent this and other crimes as commanders ([IT-95-5-I] §§84, 96).⁸⁶ Such parallel liability may be confusing^[54]. The apparent contradiction may be reconciled by arguing for a prevalence of liability for acts over liability for omission (principle of subsidiarity) if the different forms of conduct in question are temporarily and subjectively interrelated.

The mechanism of *doing Justice* in the case [IT-95-5/18]/05.04.2016[[<https://www.icty.org/en/case/karadzic>] there has been found that the perpetrator as commander of Main Staff of the army within the 1992–1995, was part of all JCEs and; thus, criminally responsible for genocide, war crimes, and crimes against humanity. Notably, the perpetrated genocide in Bosnian municipalities has been tackled outside of Srebrenica. There has been failed to prove specific genocidal intent to destroy a substantial part of the Bosnian Muslim population. Therefore, case [IT-95-5/18/05.04.2016] highlights spatial-distinction of committed crimes even toward intent.

Instead of conclusion

According to Article 6 of the EU Charter, everyone suspected of having committed a criminal offence shall be presumed innocent until proven guilty, and his liberty and security shall be secured and guaranteed in accordance with Article 48 of the same Charter (OJ C 364, 18.12.2000, p. 1; EU Convention on Fundamental Rights, 2000/C364/01; Off. J. Eur. Commun. 13.12.2000, Charter VI (Justice) [<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/DE/TXT/PDF/?uri=OJ:C:2000:364:FULL>]).

Both the Article 6 and Article 48 were used as a basis for refusing to execute an arrest warrant, despite, that it has been a European arerst warrant and should have been executed immediately in accordance with approach of expedited proceedings and execution of arrest warrants for suspects – herein, I underline suspects, not perpetrators of a crime – within the principle of “*Mutual Recognition*” (consider cases C-404/15 and C-659/15 PPV (ECLI:EU:C:2016”198); [<https://curia.europa.eu/juris/liste.jsf?num=C-404/15&language=de>]).

Regarding, principle of “*Mutual Recognition*”, I shall add that the individual is surrendered on suspicion of a crime, after which effective proceedings against him begin. In course of these proceedings, the (alleged) evidence can be rejected and the individual can be acquitted. However, the practice, so far, has shown that procedure in the so-called *fast proceedings* is not fast. For instance, case [EWHC 897/2009], [<https://www.casemine.com/judgement/uk/5a8ff76160d03e7f57eabefd>]. It deals with an accused (1) for murder of an individual (1). Within the above principle his arrest warrant is issued. After two years (2) in prison, it is proven that he is innocent. As expected – he is released. His stay in prison, however, is completely real.

Toward AWTs^[2] against **Subject 1**, I would like to add Point 192 of the legal opinion, drawn up at the request of the European Commission (2/13 ECLI:EU:C:2014:2475) [<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/DE/ALL/?uri=CELEX:62013CP0002>] stating:

“According to consistent case-law and the principle of autonomy of Union law, when concluding international agreements it is necessary to ensure that the powers of the Union and its institutions are preserved so that the international court will not give an interpretation of Union law that would bind the Union and its institutions.”

No institution in EU Member State is bound by AWTs^[2] wording; thus, allowing any other interpretations of legal issues. Let alone the execution of any orders issued by them.

Only opinions of the Court of Justice of EU have a decisive influence on autonomous Legal Systems of EU Member States. A Judicial opinion of same EU Body (1/91, 14.12.1991) states:

....“it is inadmissible for the answers of the Court, relating to the jurisdiction of the States, to be advisory without binding effect....”

Therefore, the AWTs^[2] cannot be immediately executed in any territory of an EU Member State, regardless of whether or not that State accept the Rome Statute.

(Consider also Article (1), Paragraph (2) (Main clauses) OB C313, 13.10.1996, Off. J. Eur. Commun C313, 23.10.1996, relating to extradition under a European arrest warrant.)

When executing arrest warrants the Rule of execution of a Court decision with higher supremacy is observed. The decisions of European Court of Justice and those of domestic Court Systems have higher supremacy than the Rome Statute in the EU Member States.

I would like also explicitly draw attention on Point 12 of the Agreement on Fundamental Rights of the European Union (OB C364, 18.12.2000) which states:

...“Nothing in this Framework Decision may be interpreted as prohibiting a refusal to surrender a person for whom an arrest warrant has been issued where there are reasonable grounds for believing that the warrant in question was issued for the purpose of prosecuting or punishing a person on account of...political beliefs..., or that his situation is connected with one of these grounds.”

I think, that it is clear why AWTs^[2] addressed to wrong addressee or an innocent individual (**Subject 1**) without having committed any crime contradicts minimum the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (OB C364, 18.12.2000, p. 1,) among many other legal texts.

Selected references

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- [8] According to Article 51 of the UN Charter, 'Nothing in the present Charter shall impair the inherent right of individual or collective self-defence if an armed attack occurs against a Member of the United Nations, until the Security Council has taken measures necessary to maintain international peace and security' [<https://legal.un.org/repository/art51.shtml>].
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